

Political Skills, Resilience At Work, And Public Service Motivation: A Structural Equation Model On Job Engagement Of Police Personnel In Region Xi

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APPROVAL SHEET

This dissertation titled "**POLITICAL SKILLS, RESILIENCE AT WORK, AND PUBLIC SERVICE MOTIVATION: A STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODEL ON JOB ENGAGEMENT OF POLICE PERSONNEL IN REGION XI**" was prepared and submitted by **JUAN C. CHAVEZ, JR.** in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Degree of Doctor in Public Administration has been examined and recommended for acceptance and approval.

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ABSTRACT

This study intended to establish the best-fit structural model of job engagement of police personnel in Region 11. The exogenous variables are political skills, resilience at work, and public service motivation, while the endogenous variable is job engagement. Through quota sampling, 400 police personnel from Region XI responded to the survey. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), Mean, Pearson r, and Multiple Regression were used to analyze the data. Results showed that besides respondents' very high political skills, resilience at work, public service motivation, and job performance, a significant relationship exists among between these variables. The multiple regression analysis revealed that the influence of political skills, resilience at work, and public service motivation on job engagement was 67.8%. Only Model 5 met all goodness of fit indices among the five generated models. Further analysis of the model bared that all indicators of the exogenous variables included at the beginning of the study are predictors of job performance. These manifest variables for political skills are networking ability, social astuteness, interpersonal influence, and apparent sincerity. For resilience at work, the manifest variables include living authentically, finding a calling, maintaining perspective, managing stress, building social connections, and staying healthy. For public service motivation, the manifest variables are self-sacrifice, attraction to policymaking, and compassion. On the other hand, the manifest variables for job engagement are cognitive, emotional, and physical. The results have implications for policing in the Philippines.

Keywords:- *Political skills, resilience at work, public service motivation, job performance, public administration.*

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DEDICATION

I humbly dedicate this dissertation

to my beloved

Grandfather, Sir Simon S. Chavez,

Father, Sir Juan E. Chavez, Sr.,

My wife, Dean Carmelita B. Chavez,

My son, John Carl B. Chavez,

and to this country's

Men and Women in uniform.

TO GOD BE THE GLORY!

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

A. Rationale

Scenarios depicting the low job engagement of police personnel in the country have been frequent news. The Philippine Daily Inquirer made headlines for firing two ranking police officials for their poor output in solving crime and battling illegal drugs (Cabalza, 2018). The worst scenes were the town police chiefs' relief in the Mimaropa region for low performance in anti-illegal drugs operations (Cabato, 2018).

Job engagement is essential for its impact on productivity, involving a positive state of mind and a readiness to apply to work (Sun & Bunchapattanasakda, 2019). In addition, engaged employees have high public service motivation, producing positive work-related outcomes (Antony, 2018). Besides these, job engagement positively affects performance (Ismail, Iqbal, & Nasr, 2019).

In the same vein, studies have shown a significant relationship between political skill and job engagement and that political skill can ease job stress and promote job engagement and performance (Bostanci, 2020; Kim, Karatepe, & Chung, 2019). Moreover, as a political skill, networking ability can increase employee promotability (Huang, 2020).

Further, on one hand, research has found a significant correlation between resilience at work and job engagement, whether at an individual or group level, even predicting job engagement (Cao & Chen, 2020; Cooke Cooper, Bartram, Wang, & Mei, 2019; McEwen & Boyd, 2018). However, on the other hand, a positive and significant relationship exists between public service motivation and job performance, suggesting a selection of applicants with high levels of public service motivation (Borst, Kruyen, & Lako, 2019).

There may be extensive studies on political skills, work resilience, public service motivation, and job performance. Unfortunately, the researcher had difficulty finding a survey of the relationship of these variables in a single research article; more so, a model on job engagement using these three independent variables in this study. Thus, there is a research gap concerning the best-fit model of job engagement, especially with the police personnel as the sample population. Therefore, finding a model for job engagement for police personnel is vital for job crafting by the Philippine National Police.

B. Research Objectives

This study intended to identify the best fit model for job engagement of police personnel in Region XI. Towards this end, the research set the following specific objectives:

1. To describe the political skill of the police personnel in Region XI in terms of:
 - 1.1 networking ability,
 - 1.2 interpersonal influence,
 - 1.3 social astuteness, and
 - 1.4 apparent sincerity.
2. To describe the level of resilience at work of police personnel in Region XI in terms of:
 - 2.1 living authentically,
 - 2.2 finding a calling,
 - 2.3 maintaining perspective,
 - 2.4 managing stress,
 - 2.5 building social connections, and
 - 2.6 staying healthy.

3. To ascertain the level of public service motivation of police personnel in Region XI in terms of:
 - 3.1 self-sacrifice,
 - 3.2 attraction to policy making, and
 - 3.3 compassion.
4. To ascertain the level of job engagement of police personnel in Region XI in terms of:
 - 4.1 cognitive engagement dimension,
 - 4.2 emotional engagement dimension, and
 - 4.3 physical engagement dimension.
5. To determine the relationship between:
 - 5.1 political skill and job engagement,
 - 5.2 resilience at work and work engagement, and
 - 5.3 public service motivation and job engagement.
6. To determine the significant influence of political skill, resilience at work, and public service motivation on job engagement in its combined and singular capacities.
7. To determine the best-fit structural model for job engagement.

C. Hypothesis

The significance level for this study was 0.05, which was used for testing following null hypotheses:

- There is no significant relationship among political skill, resilience at work, public service motivation, and job engagement.
- There is no singular or combined significant influence of political skills, resilience at work, or public service motivation, on job engagement.
- There is no best-fit structural model for job engagement.

D. Review of Related Literature

This section of the paper presents the literature review and studies on this investigation. This review revolves around the variables enumerated in the study's objectives: political skills, resilience at work, public service motivation, and job engagement. The literature review sources were reputable online materials such as books, journal articles, and news articles.

The political skills indicators include *networking ability*, *interpersonal influence*, *social astuteness*, and *apparent sincerity* (Ferris, Treadway, Kolodinsky, et al., 2005). Likewise, indicators for *resilience at work* include *living authentically*, *finding a calling*, *maintaining perspective*, *managing stress*, *building social connections*, and *staying healthy* (Malik & Garg, 2018). Further, the manifest variables for *public service motivation* are *self-sacrifice*, *attraction to policy making*, and *compassion* (Gan & Wang, 2013). Lastly, the manifest variables for *job engagement* are *cognitive*, *emotional*, and *physical engagement dimensions* (Kuok & Taormina, 2017).

E. Political Skill

Political skill is a construct introduced over two decades ago as a competency necessary for effective organizations. For decades, scholars have become considerably interested in organizational politics. However, the requisite competencies to practice politics successfully in the workplace seemed less interesting. Then, in the early 1980s, Pfeffer (1981) and Mintzberg (1983) advocated organizational and political perspectives, and both suggested that individuals needed to possess political skills to be effective in political environments.

Careful examination of political skill literature indicates several essential aspects in conceptualizing the political skill concept. This examination specifies four critical dimensions of political skill: *networking ability*, *interpersonal influence*, *social astuteness*, and *apparent sincerity* (Ferris et al., 2005).

Networking ability is the capacity to converse and exchange ideas and information with individuals and groups, especially those with similar interests. Individuals with this ability are experts at identifying and developing diverse contacts and people networks (Forret, 2018). People in these networks tend to hold valuable assets necessary for successful personal and organizational gains. Also, they typically subtly and quickly establish friendships and build solid and beneficial alliances and coalitions (Bhattarai, 2022; Shah, Yasir, Majid, & Javed, 2019).

Furthermore, individuals with high networking abilities positioned themselves and created opportunities to their advantage (Abushinov, 2021; Adomako, Danso, Boso, & Narteh, 2018; Lee, Yun, & Kim, 2019). These individuals are highly skilled negotiators and deal makers proficient in conflict management who become a network of contacts that can help augment shared interests (Englund, & Bucero, 2019; Schermerhorn Jr, Bachrach, & Wright, 2020). In policing, networks happen within a class. For example, police personnel form a network with barangay officials. This move is vital in sharing ideas about dealing with people and other essential ideas that would help them to discharge duties effectively. Without networking ability, police personnel may encounter difficulties in their job and eventually face failure. Hassan, Prussia, Mahsud, and Yukl (2018) clarified that networking ability depends on other factors, such as external monitoring and representation, to become influential and succeed in their career. Significantly, networking ability will help police officers and members thrive in their workplaces, even in challenges (Cullen, Gerbasi, & Chrobot-Mason, 2018; Saunders, Kotzias, & Ramchand, 2019).

Incidentally, belonging to a networking group is necessary. Networking of police officers has advantages like improved leadership techniques and communication structures, strengthened connectedness and mutual support, owing to the innovations shared by networks (Castillo De Mesa, Gómez Jacinto, López Peláez, & Palma García, 2019; Lewis, Ricard, & Klijn, 2018; Marenin, 2018). Moreover, in this era of social media reign, police personnel, government leaders, people in business, teachers, and students belong to a network where they share information about their subjects of interest (Chanana, 2020; Habibi, Mukminin, Riyanto, et al., 2018).

Interpersonal influence. Politically skilled individuals are unassuming and convincing and exert a powerful impact on people around them (Schütte, Blickle, Frieder, et al., 2018). Politically experienced people tend to influence others by adapting and attuning their behavior to different situations and eliciting their desired outcomes. They exhibit great flexibility in adjusting their behavior to varying targets of influence in different contextual settings to achieve one's goals (Deng, Guan, Wu, Erdogan, Bauer, & Yao, 2018; Veilleux, Pollert, Skinner, et al., 2019).

Interpersonal influence can build a good rapport between the police and community members. People look up to the police as persons they can trust for their safety. So, they want to be near the police all the time so that they can have better engagements (Bostanci, 2020). Wang and Hall (2019) claimed that people with solid interpersonal influence enjoy a better social life because society accepts them. Expressed differently, police personnel who establish excellent interpersonal power with the people in the community are socially accepted and enjoy a good social standing in their community. Deng et al. (2018) echoed that individuals with solid interpersonal influence gain social acceptance. Moreover, persons with good interpersonal influence have better performance outcomes that satisfy stakeholders (Schütte, Blickle, Frieder, et al., 2018).

Social astuteness. People with this political skill are smart in observing other people. They can accurately interpret others' behaviors and understand social interactions well. They have high self-awareness and concur with diverse social settings, evaluating impressions and value enhancement (Bhattarai, 2022; Kwon, 2020; McAllister, Ellen III, Perrewé, et al., 2015; Uppal, 2021).

Similarly, police personnel should have social astuteness because this provides an excellent link between leadership and public value that fosters powerful coalitions and alliances even around diverse and competing interests (Aramdhan, & Sattar, 2021; Hartley, Sancino, Bennister, & Resodihardjo, 2019). Charismatic people exemplify this political skill (Brouer, Chiu, & Wang, 2016). Moreover, policing would be difficult without social astuteness because they could not effectively carry out their policing jobs. On the contrary, social astuteness mitigates destructive behavior and facilitates positive and very high satisfaction ratings (Kwon, 2020; Xu, Chiu, & Treadway, 2019).

Police officers that are socially astute always look after people and keep them safe. This behavior can work to their advantage because people will learn to trust them, resulting in a peaceful environment (Seitz & Misra, 2020; Wang & Hall, 2019). In addition, socially astute individuals can discern people's behavior and social exchanges, which is essential in police work as it develops trust among the people (Hartley & Manzie, 2020; Uppal, 2021).

Apparent sincerity. Politically skilled individuals possess high levels of integrity and appear authentic, sincere, and genuine. They seem honest and forthright. Apparent sincerity is crucial in influencing others and winning their side (Guo, Liu, & Yain, 2020; Ma, Wu, Jiang, & Wei, 2019). The perception of other people about the other's sincerity can modify the behavior of others towards the person (Wihler, Frieder, & Blickle, 2018). It was noted by Guo et al. (2020) that influencing attempts would be successful when people perceive actors as having no ulterior motives. Individuals high in apparent sincerity can inspire trust and confidence in people because their actions are not manipulative or coercive (Wang, Luo, Zhang, & Guo, 2019; Wihler et al., 2018).

Consequently, others misunderstood apparent sincerity as fake sincerity because of the word "apparent." However, people will notice sincerity in words and actions. People hear sincerity even in voices (Barkacs, 2021). Furthermore, research proved that apparent sincerity could enhance interpersonal relationships between people (Maher, Ejaz, Nguyen, & Ferris, 2021). In addition, apparent sincerity can give the impression of genuine care and support, releasing any forms of pressure that the rule of man has generated, thus promoting understanding, respect, and trust (Hasan, Hayek, Williams Jr, Pane-Haden, & Gelvez, 2020; Kim, LePine, & Chun, 2018; Xu, Yang, Guo, & Zhang, 2019).

To rephrase, leaders should convey their apparent sincerity through genuine service to influence others to trust them, mainly because people are good at differentiating authentic actions from pretenses (Barkacs, 2021; Kranefeld, Blickle, & Meurs, 2020; Wee, Ahmad, Sadik, Abd Razak, & Marmaya, 2019). Therefore, police personnel must be careful in interacting with the community to earn their trust (Ma et al., 2019).

The literature on political skills taught the researcher that its four dimensions are related yet remain distinct constructs. In addition, the literature pointed to the fact that political skill is a set of long-established social competencies (Blickle, Frieder, & Ferris, 2018; Ferris, Berkson, Kaplan, et al., 2005; Mintzberg, 1983). Significantly, the readings taught that political skill is crucial for police personnel because it can give them the ability to understand their coworkers effectively, given the nature of their job. With such understanding, they could encourage others to act towards achieving personal and organizational objectives. In addition, the literature on political skills gives ample information about work-related competencies. Finally, it conveys that people can attain political skills through experience, training, and practice. The insinuation is that individuals benefit from experiences that cultivate political skills, regardless of inherent political capabilities.

F. Resilience at Work

Resilience refers to an individual's emotional endurance, characterized by a person's courage, adaptability, persistence, and perseverance in the wake of crisis and life's misfortunes (Taormina, 2015). With determination and stability, the individual can adapt to calamity, strain, suffering, and significant life stressors (Malik & Garg, 2018; Platania, Castellano, Petralia, et al., 2020).

Incidentally, resilience can shield a person from mental illness (Etilé, Frijters, Johnston, & Shields, 2021). A resilient individual has self-esteem, believes in his self-efficacy, and possesses problem-solving skills. Resilience is adapting well in times of crisis, hardships, trauma, tragedy, and even significant sources of threat. These researchers abstracted resilience as the individual's relative susceptibility to the maladaptive effects of their environment (Etilé et al., 2021; Malik et al., 2018; Platania et al., 2020; Southwick et al., 2012; & Taormina, 2015).

People assume that police personnel are resilient, having survived the contemporary stress they face daily. Police must be resilient at work to withstand challenges and surmount job difficulties. To achieve resilience of mind and body, police personnel undergo proper training because various factors like trauma, threats, tragedies, and other challenges combined may cause police resilience to weaken (Chitra & Karunanidhi, 2021; Krause & Halkitis, 2020; Manerin, 2018).

Consequently, in today's world, transformations escalate and continuously occur due to global competition, technological revolutions, organizational restructuring, and contemporary organizations. Nevertheless, these transformations opened employees' vulnerabilities to stressful work environments (Malik & Garg, 2018; Malik & Garg, 2020). Thus, the development of resilience becomes essential to support employees working in an arduous environment. This resilience would help them to adapt to challenging situations effectively. Scholars and organizational practitioners view resilience as the new criterion for professional advancement, given its characteristics of adaptability, flexibility, and strength of purpose (Cooper, Brown, Rees, & Leslie, 2020; Linnenluecke, 2017; Malik & Garg, 2020).

Therefore, in the present era of economic uncertainty and intense competitiveness, organizations that instill resilience among their employees will have a strong advantage. However, resilience in the workplace context is still a relatively unexplored phenomenon. Nevertheless, researchers have affirmed the significance of resilience and reported its vital role in fostering employees' well-being and performance (Kim, 2020; Lee, Yahiaoui, Lee, & Cooke, 2022; Ukhova, 2020). Also, over time, resilience studies resulted in many operational definitions, but mostly, resilience is bouncing back from adversity (Malik et al., 2018; Platania et al., 2020; Taormina, 2015).

Significantly, researchers have observed a shift from the dispositional view of resilience, suggesting that individuals can develop the dynamic process of resilience through thoughtful interaction with the external environment (Sharma & Sharma, 2020; Srivastava, 2020). Furthermore, developing resilience is significant since it submits that rather than being a genetic trait, resilience is an adaptable epiphenomenon that employees can develop through appropriate training (Hollis, 2020; Lee, Choi, & Kwon, 2019).

In other words, once an individual develops resilience, he can have the capability of bouncing back from adversity, conflict, and failure. In sustaining resilience, the individual has to maintain a discourse and interaction. Resilience is seen as dynamic, integrated, unfolding over time and through events, evolving patterns, and dependent on contingency. In this study, resilience at work denotes *living authentically, finding a calling, maintaining perspective, managing stress, building social connections, and staying healthy* (Malik & Garg, 2018).

Living authentically pertains to employees' work attitudes and behaviors consistent with their values rather than other peoples' expectations (Chen & Murphy, 2019; Gino, Sezer, & Huang, 2020; Song, Wang, & Zhao, 2021). In addition, authentic living significantly predicts hedonic and eudaimonic well-being (Yu, Li, & Xiao, 2020). The implication is that only by authentic living can a person live the good life, expressing himself and experiencing vitality, self-actualization, and well-being (Bernecker & Becker, 2021; Niemiec, 2014; Sutton 2020).

Authentic living leads to happiness. However, research shows that to attain a happy life, a person has to exercise self-control because living at the extremes may overturn the tables (Bernecker & Bernecker, 2021; Van den Bosch, Taris, Schaufeli, Peeters, & Reijseger, 2019). As employees of the Philippine National Police (PNP), police personnel must always exercise self-control, primarily because their job requires them to do so. Policing is not an easy job. The police personnel is often in situations that test their patience and resilience. Without self-control, their lot may end in catastrophe leading to an unhappy life as others had before them. Therefore, self-control is fundamental to self-regulation (Converse, Juarez, & Hennecke, 2019; Sosik, Chun, Ete, Arenas, & Scherer, 2019).

Finding a calling means pursuing a passion or a vocation, which brings more profound organizational commitment, thus reducing aberrant behaviors and the intention to leave (Afsar, Umrani, & Khan, 2019). When individuals find their calling, persistence drives them to such, and they are unstoppable (Cavanaugh, 2021; Yeung, 2021). Those still looking for their "calling" ventured fearlessly into the unknown (Jaiswal, 2019).

Research shows that living a calling would not happen unless an individual experiences a person-environment fit, career commitment, and has a sense of the meaning of their work (Duffy, Douglass, Gensmer, England, & Kim, 2019). This statement is true with police personnel. For example, a study on a law enforcement agency in the Midwest United States found the importance of calling as an antecedent to policing. Police personnel with a higher sense of calling displayed more job satisfaction and contentment with their career (Chen, May, Schwoerer, & Augelli, 2018).

Maintaining perspective is the third indicator of resilience at work. Incidentally, different workspaces offer varied perspectives. For instance, employees may have different views about work stress even though it is a daily experience. For example, in police work, the stress level is very high. However, police personnel saw it as a standard expectation because of the nature of their work: maintaining peace and order and fighting criminals. Police stress is extreme in some parts of the world (Humayon, Raza, Amir, et al., 2018), which leads to suicide and other negative results (Gomes, de Araújo, & Gomes, 2018; Queirós, Passos, Bártolo, et al., 2020).

Nevertheless, maintaining a proper perspective about the job can help with its negative aspects. For example, understanding police interaction processes and applying other scientific methods to reduce work-related stress and improve policing are good perspectives for better job appreciation (Rantatalo & Karp, 2018; Willis & Mastrofski, 2018; Wolter, Santa Maria, Georg, et al., 2021)

Managing stress is an essential indicator of resilience at work. Research shows a very high-stress level among law enforcement personnel considering the nature of their work (Humayon et al., 2018; Gomes et al., 2018; Queiros et al., 2020), especially in complex sites (Marois, Cloutier, Saunier, et al., 2019). There have been several studies on stress so that individuals and organizations may find ways to manage stress effectively. For example, police officers in Poland have some methods of managing their stress, like communicating with their families, surfing the internet, and watching TV. They find these methods effective in combating workplace stress (Cieślak, Kielan, Olejniczak, et al., 2020).

In Southeast Nigeria, staff of the Nigeria Police Force resorted to Rational Emotive Occupational Health Coaching (REOHC) to manage work-related stress and found the REOHC program a practical approach for managing this phenomenon (Onyishi, Ede, Ossai, et al., 2021). Moreover, some police officers are experiencing post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), anxiety, and depression. Some stressors reported include culture, organizational change, leadership, working hours, and workloads. To manage these stressors, they promote counseling, training, and changes in the workplace to address and mitigate mental health issues (Demou, Hale, & Hunt, 2020). In others, they resort to spirituality—introspection, meditation, and meaningful work in shielding against stress and other stress-related illnesses (Subhashini, 2018), while the Philippine National Police opt for relaxation techniques and social support to manage stress at work (Gutierrez, Ilagan, Curtis, et al., 2015).

Building social connections is vital for cultivating resilience at work. Social relationships nowadays are quickly happening because of technology and social media exposure. Whether technology brings people closer or apart, the truth is that technology is fundamental to the coming together of society, whether resulting in positive or negative impacts (Brey, 2018; Karintseva, Melnyk, Kubatko, et al., 2019).

However, research also shows that building social connections is crucial because they nurture personal relationships and establish rapport and social engagements. Individuals belonging to the same group become highly connected social partners (Kulahci & Quinn, 2019; Waycott, Vetere, & Ozanne, 2019).

Staying healthy is a fundamental requirement for life's enjoyment. Health is a person's most incredible wealth (Fletcher, Parker, Smith, & Robinson, 2020). Moreover, a healthy lifestyle can prevent health deterioration even in old age (le May & Elbourne, 2019). For police personnel to stay healthy, it is not only an individual decision but requires health-oriented leadership (HoL). Research shows that HoL directly impacts the physical and mental health of police personnel, promoting their well-being (Santa Maria, Wolter, Gusy, et al., 2019).

Incidentally, police officers' job characteristics are unique, jeopardizing their health and well-being. Thus, proactive planning is necessary to promote police well-being and satisfaction with the system (Van Thielen, Bauwens, Audenaert, et al., 2018). In addition, job characteristics, demands, and resources often pose emotional pressure and mental strain in police work. So, providing enough resources for police work can improve police stress (Wolter, Santa Maria, Wörfel, et al., 2019).

The literature on resilience at work offered the research ample knowledge on the strategies for staying resilient at work. Employees face different challenging situations and stressors in the workplace, and the spirit of resilience is an effective mechanism for remaining intense and focused. The literature on resilience at work points to living authentically, finding a calling, maintaining perspective, managing stress, building social connections, and staying healthy are practical tools to carry in the workplace.

G. Public Service Motivation

Scholars and practitioners in public administration have widely studied public service motivation (PSM). PSM is the desire to contribute to society's well-being. Research findings revealed that police officers with a higher level of public service motivation have higher levels of job satisfaction, mediated by person-job and person-organization fits (Prymakova & Vandenabeele, 2020). Besides this, PSM intervenes in the relationship between leadership behaviors and taking-charge behavior among police officers (Homburg, Vogel, & Weiherl, 2019).

Moreover, researchers investigate public service motivation to decipher the intents and motivations of people joining the public sector and improve public servants' expected performance in delivering public services (Breugh, Ritz, & Alfes, 2018; Christensen, Paarlberg, & Perry, 2017). The study of PSM is

beneficial in driving organizational trust, job satisfaction, innovation, and commitment (Andersen, Jensen, & Kjeldsen, 2020; Harari, Herst, Parola, & Carmona, 2017; Levitats & Vigoda-Gadot, 2017; Miao, Newman, Schwarz, & Cooper, 2018).

While delving into public service motivation, it is important to discuss its indicators: *self-sacrifice*, *attraction to policymaking*, and *compassion* (Gan & Wang, 2013). These three indicators came from the original work of Perry (1996) that Gan and Wang (2013) have shortened from 24 items to 14 items to investigate the Chinese civil servants in Kunming City.

Self-sacrifice is giving up something for the welfare of others. Consequently, all living things embody a virtue of self-sacrifice (Bélanger, Schumpe, Menon, et al., 2018). For example, during the COVID-19 pandemic, the world has seen the self-sacrifice of health care professionals, the military, and the police. They risked fearlessly taking care of other people (Gil-Gimeno & Sánchez Capdequí, 2021). Unfortunately, several essential workers have died because of it (Hassanian-Moghaddam, Zamani, & Kolahi, 2020; Majeed, Molokhia, Pankhania, et al., 2020; The Lancet, 2020).

Moreover, policing is a vocation that entails self-sacrifice for the good of the entire community. Police officers are ready to lay down their lives for others to live peacefully, as they are watchdogs for peace and order in the community (Javdani, 2019; Van Ackeren & Archer, 2018). Nevertheless, even with the self-sacrificial nature of police work, the demands of their work may lead to exhaustion, stress, and burnout (Humayon, Raza, Amir, et al., 2018; Murad, Jiatong, Shahzad, et al., 2021; Nevels, Burch, Wirth, et al., 2021).

Attraction to policymaking. It is the forceful motive of individuals to join the police force. However, studies show that appeal to policymaking restrains the correlation between fairness and outcomes. Therefore, it significantly impacts those with little attraction to policymaking (Jensen, Kjeldsen, & Vestergaard, 2020; Quratulain, Khan, & Sabharwal, 2019). Policy changes can also affect the motivation of government employees toward public service. For example, the personality, gender, educational background, and previous job of police officers can influence attraction to policymaking (Piatak, Douglas, & Raudla, 2020; Van Witteloostuijn, Esteve, & Boyne, 2017). In other words, employees could have different takes on policy changes. For example, those with a person-organization fit may welcome policy changes, but others may not. In another study, job attributes, such as the nature of work and the institution's type, whether government or non-profit organization, influence employees' dimensions of public service motivation.

Compassion means to suffer together. Compassionate people go out to help others in need and find satisfaction. There are studies about police compassion coupled with either burnout, compassion fatigue, or compassion satisfaction (Grant, Lavery, & Decarlo, 2019; Papazoglou, Koskelainen, & Stuewe, 2018; Stancel, Russo, Koskelainen, et al., 2019). Burnout and compassion fatigue have a positive correlation, while compassion fatigue and compassion satisfaction have a negative relationship. Interestingly, one study in North America reported police officers' compassion satisfaction rate at 38% and compassion fatigue at 23% (Andersen, Papazoglou, & Collins, 2018).

People expect police officers to be solid and sharp due to their work's nature (Courpasson & Monties, 2017; Todak, 2017). However, frequent exposure to stress results in compassion fatigue that weakens their physical, mental, and emotional well-being (Burnett, Sheard, & St Clair-Thompson, 2020). Policing has very demanding roles, causing adverse effects over time. Hence, police agencies must introduce effective coping measures for their personnel's welfare (Papazoglou, Marans, Keese, et al., 2020).

This literature review on PSM exposed the realities and challenges of police work. Police personnel are human beings that join law enforcement with personal motives. Some joined the force because of job security, better pay, and career advancement opportunities, to mention a few. Regrettably, there is no more stable employer than the government. Others join public service because of public service motivation,

indicating self-sacrifice, compassion, attraction to policymaking, and commitment to the public interest. The list can be lengthy.

H. Job Engagement

Job engagement is a person's enthusiasm for doing the job. It is a catalyst for growth both by the employee and the company (Jaharuddin & Zainol, 2019). Brunetto, Farr-Wharton, B., Farr-Wharton, R., Shacklock, Azzopardi, Saccon, and Shriberg (2020) found the influence of job engagement on police productivity. Yin (2018) observed that employees who are enthusiastic about their job perform better and find it fulfilling. However, job engagement does not happen without some dimensions to it. For instance, dimensions are organization-based self-esteem and satisfaction with life (Toth, Heinänen, & Nisula, 2020), task performance (Basit, 2019), and employee profile and job characteristics (Eldor & Harpaz, 2016; Gillet, Morin, Jeoffrion, et al., 2020). This study's job engagement dimensions are *cognitive engagement*, *emotional engagement*, and *physical engagement dimensions* (Kuok & Taormina, 2017).

Cognitive Work Engagement. The concept of focus to improve effectiveness is what the mental aspect of job engagement is all about. People must work with judgment and mindfulness to become effective (Kuok & Taormina, 2017). Notionally, individuals who are cognitively engaged in their jobs have positive thoughts. Because of this, they pay more attention to their work, with high effectiveness and productivity (Basinska & Dåderman, 2019; Osborne & Hammoud, 2017).

Consequently, supervisors' negative emotions can result in negative and positive employee behaviors. Although supervisors' negative emotions can lead to high cognitive work engagement levels, the downside is a family decline (Chan, Kalliath, & Cheng, 2020), which may lead to turnover intention. Thus managers must take measures to improve relationships in the workplace through teamwork or empower them to work independently (Gupta & Shaheen, 2017).

Research shows that justice and support of supervisors positively affect the work engagement of police officers (Piotrowski, Rawat, & Boe, 2021), implying the need to maintain harmonious employer-employee and supervisor-employee relationships in general.

Emotional Work Engagement involves workers' positive emotional attachment to tasks and activities, such as pride, enthusiasm, and excitement toward task completion (Kuok & Taormina, 2017). Emotional work engagement reduces counterproductive behavior for conscientious and emotionally stable employees, although it can negatively influence emotionally unstable employees (Chen, Richard, Boncoeur, & Ford Jr, 2020). Indeed, emotional work engagement does not always produce a positive vibe, as emotional labor may result in stress and burnout, police personnel or not (Jeung, Kim, & Chang, 2018).

Nevertheless, understanding the negative aspect of emotional engagement and identifying its antecedents is essential to prevent counterproductive behaviors. Precursors include a lack of administrative support and justice (Piotrowski, Rawat, & Boe, 2021), role ambiguity, ethical tension, conflict, personality trait (Sl Shbail, Salleh, & Mohd, 2018), and high job demands (Sabagh, Hall, & Saroyan, 2018) negatively contribute to emotional work engagement. Opportunely, research shows that emotional intelligence (EI) has a positive association with positive employee attitudes. Thus, reinforcing EI through interventions could help the problem of emotional exhaustion that leads to counterproductive behaviors at work (Extremera, Mérida-López, Sánchez-Álvarez, & Quintana-Orts, 2018; Jung & Yoon, 2012; Susanti, & Alwansyah, 2021).

Physical Work Engagement is bodily participation in any kind of occupation. Although people exert varying physical efforts to complete their tasks, they spend enormous energy. Physical work engagement accounts for the energy consumed at work and the intensity and frequency of its use (Kuok & Taormina, 2017). Physical engagement at work does not confine to activities directly affecting the tasks. There are

other tasks indirectly associated with it. For example, workplace exercise at least once or twice a week could help employees achieve vigor that can bolster their physical work engagement (Jindo, Kai, Kitano, Tsunoda, Nagamatsu, & Arao, 2020).

Similarly, physical work engagement is vital for task completion in any workplace setup. However, physical activities are crucial to improving mental well-being and productivity. Productivity does not only materialize with physical work engagement *per se*. It involves other physical activities to improve brainwork. For example, the research found that sitting most of the time lessens mental well-being. However, physical activities can improve employees' mental well-being and productivity (Grimani, Aboagye, & Kwak, 2019; Puig-Ribera, Martínez-Lemos, Giné-Garriga, et al., 2015).

The literature on job engagement provided the research with much-needed arguments for this study. The literature cited the importance of cognitive work engagement (e.g., prudent judgment), emotional work engagement (e.g., enthusiasm and emotional work attachments), and physical work engagement (e.g., physical efforts, like exercise) to achieve work productivity and optimum job performance.

I. Correlation between Measures

Studies have shown a significant relationship between *political skills* and *work engagement*. Recently, Bostanci (2020) found a moderate, positive, and meaningful relationship between the dimensions of political skill: social astuteness, interpersonal influence skill, networking ability, apparent sincerity, and the level of work engagement. Philip (2021) also found that political skill strengthened the relationship between proactive personality and work engagement. Moreover, Basit (2020) found a good impact of political skills on job performance. Another study found the influence of political skills in mitigating job dissatisfaction, encouraging employees to engage more in their jobs to achieve better work outcomes (De Clercq, Haq, Azeem, & Ahmad, 2019).

On the other hand, Cooke, Cooper, Bartram, Wang, and Mei (2019) found a significant relationship between *resilience at work* and *work engagement*. Cao and Chen (2020) stressed a direct, positive, and meaningful relationship between resilience and work engagement. Moreover, they found that resilience is a predictor of work engagement. Malik and Grag (2020) also claimed that employee resilience could build a highly engaged workforce, which suggests the influencing factor of resilience at work on work engagement.

Additionally, there is a positive correlation between resilience at work and job performance (Kašpárková, Vaculík, Procházka, & Schaufeli, 2018). Both individual and team resilience at work influence job performance to an optimum level (McEwen & Boyd, 2018).

Likewise, Borst, Kruyen, & Lako's (2019) study discovered a positive and significant correlation between *public service motivation* and *work engagement*. They also suggested selecting employees with high levels of public service motivation, implying that public service motivation is a predictor of work engagement. In addition, Mussagulova (2020) found that higher PSM strengthens the positive impact of some job resources on work engagement, highlighting the importance of PSM in work engagement as both an enhancer and a coping mechanism.

Likewise, higher PSM congruently impacts public service engagements (Schwarz, Eva, & Newman, 2020) in the government sector, especially if job resources are available (Boyd, Nowell, Yang, & Hano, 2018; Rajagukguk & Desiana, 2021).

In synthesis, the correlation between measures provided ample knowledge and background of the topics in this study. The literature also elucidated the connection between political skills, resilience at work, public service motivation, and job performance. Moreover, the literature proved that these variables significantly improve job performance. Overall, the writings of renowned scholars contributed to understanding the topics at hand, helped formulate the theoretical framework, and developed the questionnaire.

J. Theoretical Framework

Three theories became the foundation of this study because it discusses three topics that relate to each other. These are necessary ideas that serve as foundational anchors of this investigation. In this paper, the anchor theories are Signaling Theory (Spence, 1978), Resilience Theory (Garmezy, 1991), and Moral Foundations Theory (Haidt, 2013). These essential theories explain the ideas purported in this study. Additionally, these theories helped the researcher observe and analyze the data and describe the effects of the exogenous variables on the endogenous variable in the study.

The signaling theory (ST) (Spence, 1974) is a central concept that explains the relationship between political skills and job engagement. It assumes that an individual sends signals to others to transmit information about their abilities, intentions, and actions to influence observers' beliefs and reduce ambiguity. For example, consider how politically-skilled police personnel may signal their effective work performance and personal character by developing solid relationships with their peers and the community. Further, in terms of success at work, police personnel may be able to leverage the signals about themselves and their work, thus, achieving success (Magnusen, Mondello, Kim, & Ferris, 2011; Magnusen, McAllister, Kim, Perrewé, & Ferris, 2017; Treadway, Adams, Hanes, Perrewé, Magnusen, & Ferris, 2014).

The resilience theory (RT) (Garmezy, 1991) argues that people face adversities, and how they deal with hardships, dangers, or misfortunes matters most. With this argument, resilience theory supports the signaling hypothesis. For instance, police work has many risks. So, police personnel receives signals about work hazards in their operations. These signals help police to recognize the problem signs and help them realize the problems and think of ways to deal with them effectively. In this stage comes resilience. Adversities test human resilience. Ledesma (2014) and Luthans (2002) stressed that resilience is the ability to bounce back from adversity, frustration, and misfortune. It is a stable trajectory of healthy functioning after a highly adverse event (Bonanno, 2021). With the signals received by police personnel, their resilience becomes more intense because either they have bounced back from experience or learned from their colleagues' experiences in the field.

Finally, the Moral Foundation Theory (MFT) (Graham, Haidt, Koleva, Motyl, Iyer, Wojcik, & Ditto, 2013; Haidt, 2013) supports the signaling and resilience theories as it identifies the triggers for moral intuitions, especially for public service motivation. These triggers come from the six moral foundations: care/harm, fairness/cheating, loyalty/betrayal, authority/subversion, sanctity/degradation, and liberty/oppression. MFT postulates that moral judgment comes from automatic processes and intuitions than conscious reasoning. In other words, the person responds to something based on his moral footing, and the response becomes intuitive. The moral or ethical foundation theory locates the source of attention and belief elicitation, which is the representation of a person's emotional state (such as the logic of appropriateness), and specific types of motivated behaviors (Fehr, Yam, & Dang, 2015; Weaver, Reynolds, & Brown, 2014). Thus, determining the location of motivation to serve the public. In context, the moral foundation theory identifies the location or roots of police personnel's public service motivation. Ethics sifts the signals they receive, whether positive or negative (care/harm, fairness/cheating, loyalty/betrayal, authority/subversion, sanctity/degradation, and liberty/oppression), and appropriates the response. The response becomes automatic as they develop resilience from their experiences weld by time.

K. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 is the conceptual model of the study illustrating the interrelationships of the exogenous variables and their direct causal relationship with job engagement. The exogenous variables in this study include political skills, resilience at work, and public service motivation. The endogenous variable is job engagement.

Fig. 1: Conceptual Model of the Study Showing the Interrelationships of the Exogenous Variables and their Direct Causal Relationship with Job Engagement

Legend:

- | | | |
|------------------------------|----------------------------------|--------------------------------------|
| NA – networking ability | MP – maintaining perspective | AM – attraction to policymaking |
| II – interpersonal influence | MS – managing stress | CO – compassion |
| SA – social astuteness | BC – building social connections | CED – cognitive engagement dimension |
| AS – apparent sincerity | SH – studying healthy | EED – emotional engagement dimension |
| LA – living authentically | SS – self-sacrifice | PED – physical engagement dimension |
| FC – finding calling | | |

The indicators of political skills are networking ability, interpersonal influence, social astuteness, and apparent sincerity (Ferris et al., 2005). For resilience at work, the indicators are authentic living, finding a calling, maintaining perspective, managing stress, building social connections, and staying healthy (Malik & Garg, 2018). Finally, public service motivation involves self-sacrifice, attraction to policymaking, and compassion (Perry, 1996), while job engagement is cognitive, emotional, and physical (Kuok & Taormina, 2017). Figure 1 illustrates the interplay of these variables.

To understand these concepts, here is a brief definition for each. *Networking ability* means the skill of building relationships with influential people at work and using these connections to make things happen at work. *Interpersonal experience* refers to developing a good rapport and communicating effectively with others. *Social astuteness* refers to the skill of instinctively knowing the right things to say or do to influence others. Finally, *apparent authority* refers to the ability to pay close attention to people’s facial expressions and show genuine interest in others.

On the other hand, *living authentically* means that a person holds fast to his work values. *Finding a calling* refers to work that helps fulfill life's purpose. *Maintaining perspective* means that negativity and intimidation at work do not affect the person. *Managing stress* means that the person has developed reliable ways to relax under pressure at work. *Building social connection* refers to a person's robust and reliable network of supportive colleagues at work. *Finally, staying healthy* denotes having a good level of physical fitness and healthy eating habits.

Further, *self-sacrifice* signifies putting duty before self and making enormous sacrifices for the good of society. *Attraction to policymaking* denotes sharing views on public policies with others and involving oneself in public programs that benefit the community. *Finally, compassion* means feeling sympathetic for the plight of the underprivileged and making a difference in society.

Furthermore, *cognitive work engagement* suggests the mind's full engagement at work. *Emotional work engagement* denotes work enthusiasm and a sense of gratification with work performance. *Finally, physical work engagement* signifies a high level of energy and stamina for work while finding work physically stimulating.

L. Significance of the Study

The findings of this study may become a guiding principle and a model for human resource management in the public and private sectors. In general, employers may gain from this study as this can be a good source of information and data on factors inclined towards job engagement. In addition, the findings of this study may give employers and employees a mutual benefit that can redound to the organization's growth and employees' careers.

Remarkably, the Philippine National Police may benefit from this study because the findings may prompt the officials on the traits acceptable to the employees, which can result in an optimized job engagement. Also, this study may benefit the rest of the police personnel occupying the lower level position, and the non-commissioned officers can benefit from the findings of this study by challenging them to become good police officers motivated to serve and firmly committed. In the same vein, social researchers may find this study helpful as this may give new knowledge in the world of public administration.

M. Definition of Terms

The operational definitions of terms are provided here to have a common understanding of these concepts.

- Political Skills. In this study, political skills refer to the networking ability, interpersonal influence, social astuteness, and apparent sincerity of police personnel.
- Resilience at Work refers to the following indicators authentic living, finding a calling, maintaining perspective, managing stress, building social connections, and staying healthy.
- Public Service Motivation. The term refers to the level of self-sacrifice, attraction to policy making, and compassion of the police personnel.
- Job engagement refers to the cognitive, emotional, and physical work engagement dimensions of the police personnel in Region 11.
- Police officers refer to the police officers with ranks ranging from Police Officer 1 to Senior Police Officer IV assigned in Region XI.

CHAPTER 2

METHOD

In this chapter is discussed the method used in this study, including the description of the research design, research locale, population and sample, research instrument, the process of collecting the data, statistical tools, and the ethical considerations observed in conducting this study.

A. Research Design

This study used structural equation modeling (SEM) to analyze structural relationships between the observed and latent variables. SEM represents an analytical approach for evaluating a priori theory-driven data about causal relations among exogenous (measured) and endogenous (latent) variables. However, SEM is not a simple statistical technique because it conceptualizes models, identifies parameters and estimations, assesses model fits, and re-specifies models between correlation data (Gana & Broc, 2019; Keith, 2019; Mueller & Hancock, 2018). Nevertheless, SEM is increasingly popular in Social Sciences, especially among academic researchers and those undergoing doctoral dissertations (Civelek, 2018; Tarka, 2018).

Structural equation modeling (SEM) is a prevailing, multivariate method used in testing multivariate causal relationships, including the indirect and direct effects on pre-assumed causal relationships (Fan, Chen, Shirkey, John, Wu, Park, & Shao, 2016; Grace, Scheiner, & Schoolmaster Jr, 2015). For example, in this study, the use of SEM explained what determines the job engagement of the police personnel in Region XI. These entail causal models, a set of mathematical equations (also called structural equations), and a graph depicting the hypothesized causal structure. Usually, a causal analysis complements structural equation modeling, providing an evaluation of proposed hypotheses against available data. Also, regression analysis provides a foundation for the causal analysis of data (Bongers, Forré, Peters, & Mooij, 2021; Grace & Irvine, 2020; Ma, Zhou, & Yang, 2020; Verma & Pearl, 2022).

B. Research Locale

In Figure 2 is presented the locale of the study, which is Region 11, the Davao Region, comprised of Davao de Oro, Davao del Norte, Davao Oriental, Davao del Sur, and Davao Occidental. Davao Region is in the southeastern location of Mindanao. It has six cities: Davao, Digos, Mati, Panabo, Samal, and Tagum. Davao Region has a land area of 20,357 sq. km. encompassing 43 municipalities, 11 congressional districts, and 1,162 barangays. Its primer city, the City of Davao, has a land area of 2,443.6 sq. km.

Davao de Oro, whose capital is Nabunturan, was formerly named Compostela Valley province. It was part of Davao del Norte before, but the ratification of Republic Act 8470 on March 8, 1998, formally separated it. Compostela Valley was renamed Davao de Oro on April 17, 2019, through Republic Act 11297. Davao de Oro has two legislative districts, 11 municipalities, and 237 barangays. Its capital is Nabunturan. Davao de Oro occupies 14.73 percent of the total land area of the Davao region.

Fig. 2: Map of the Philippines and Davao Region

On the other hand, Davao Oriental has two legislative districts, one city, ten municipalities, and 183 barangays. Moreover, Davao del Sur's capital city is Digos. As a result, Davao del Sur has only one congressional district, one city, nine municipalities, and 232 barangays. Davao City is within Davao del Sur but is independent of the province. Therefore, its inclusion in Davao del Sur is for geographic and statistical purposes only. There are three congressional districts in Davao City with 182 barangays.

Davao Occidental, whose capital is the municipality of Malita, is the newest province in the Philippines. Republic Act 10360, signed by President Benigno Aquino III on January 14, 2013, created the province of Davao Occidental. It comprises one congressional district, five municipalities, and 105 barangays (PhilAtlas, 2022).

C. Population and Sample

Four hundred personnel comprised the sample of this study, chosen through quota sampling. Quota sampling has an advantage because, besides its easy process, it ensures that groups are not over-represented. Still, it achieves the best representation of respondents in the final sample because the survey reflects the whole population with the same characteristic (Ilyasu & Etikan, 2021). For this study, the breakdown of respondents was as follows: Police Regional Office XI (PROXI) had 100 samples because it had the most police personnel. Davao City Police Office (DCPO) had 50, Davao del Sur (50), Davao del Norte (50), Davao Oriental (50), Davao de Oro (50), and Davao Occidental (50). The total was 400.

The study included the police personnel with the ranks of Senior Police Officer IV (Police Executive Master Sergeant), Senior Police Officer III (Police Chief Master Sergeant), Senior Police Officer II (Police Senior Master Sergeant), Senior Police Officer I (Police Master Sergeant), Police Officer III (Police Staff Sergeant), Police Officer II (Police Corporal), and Police Officer I

(Patrolman/Patrolwoman). Excluded were police personnel with higher ranks beyond SPO4.

The researcher asked for the help of the provincial director in recruiting the respondents since the researcher could not directly approach the target respondent without getting permission form or passing through the top officials. Importantly, since the respondents' participation was voluntary, the respondents could withdraw their participation in the survey if they felt some discomfort for any reason while answering the questionnaire. Their withdrawal would not constitute any fine, penalty, or accountability, and this decision would be respected by the researcher. The researcher understood the importance of the respondents' free and informed decision; therefore, the participants could withdraw their participation anytime without fear of coercion or any charge in judicial or quasi-judicial bodies. The welfare of the respondents was always the primordial concern of the researcher.

D. Research Instrument

This study used four survey questionnaires: The political skills inventory, resilience at work scale, public service motivation, and work engagement scales. These instruments were adapted from standard questionnaires but modified to fit the study's goals. Ferris et al. (2005) developed the Political Skills Inventory. The Resilience at Work was by Malik & Garg (2018), the Public Service Motivation questionnaire was by Perry (1996), and the Work Engagement Inventory was by Kuok & Taormina (2017). The panel of experts validated the questionnaires and gave them a 4.81 validity index.

Moreover, the pilot testing of the independent variables yielded an alpha of .969 for political skills, .957 for resilience at work, and .952 for public service motivation. The dependent variable, job performance, yielded an alpha of .977. All Cronbach Alpha values were above .90, indicating an excellent internal consistency of the items. Below are the rating scales used to interpret the data derived from each questionnaire.

E. Guide in interpreting data

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	The respondents always manifested the idea/values/act stipulated in the survey item.
3.40 - 4.19	High	The respondents often manifested the idea/values/act stipulated in the survey item.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderate	The respondents sometimes manifested the idea/values/act stipulated in the survey item.
1.80 - 2.59	Low	The respondents rarely manifested the idea/values/act stipulated in the survey item.
1.00 - 1.79	Very Low	The respondents never manifested the idea/values/act stipulated in the survey item.

F. Data Collection

These were the steps followed in collecting the data for this study. *First*, the researcher secured an endorsement from the graduate school dean as an attachment to the letter to the police regional director. *Second*, the researcher sent a communication to the police provincial offices in the region (PROXI), Compostela Valley, Davao del Norte, Davao Oriental, Davao del Sur, Davao Occidental, Davao City, and the Regional Mobile Force Battalion informing them of the approval by the Police Regional Director to conduct the study. After receiving the communication, the researcher distributed the Informed Consent Form (ICF) to the respondents for their signature. Once the respondents signed the ICF, they received the questionnaires, which they accomplished for one week. Finally, the researcher arranged the retrieval of the questionnaires with the police provincial office. Encoding of responses and analysis of data followed immediately, then the interpretation of data.

G. Statistical Tools

The analysis of data used these statistical tools:

Mean described the levels of political skills, resilience at work, public service motivation, and job engagement of the respondents.

Pearson r revealed the significance of the relationship between political skills, resilience at work, public service motivation, and job engagement.

Regression Analysis determined the functional relationships between two or more variables in this study so that a causal analysis (how one or more variables affect changes in another variable) could be possible.

The Structural Equation Model characterized a causal system with a set of variables in this study and a bunch of equations describing how each variable depends upon its immediate causal predecessors.

Ethical Considerations This study applied several ethical safeguards based on the assessment points required by the university's ethics research committee.

- **Voluntary Participation.** The researcher enlightened the respondents on the purpose and objectives of the study, including the nature of their participation. In this way, the target samples could give an informed decision regarding their involvement in the research. Although fortunately, no respondents dropped their participation in the middle of the survey. Through they were free to voluntary withdraw from the study at

any time. Even if they had dropped, no penalties, threats, or intimidation would have been conveyed or applied to them.

- **Privacy and Confidentiality.** Ethics dictates keeping the respondents' details private and confidential. In abiding by this rule, the researcher did not collect any information traceable to the respondents. Furthermore, the survey instrument had no names or identifiers of the respondents, and the data encoding involved codes in keeping the identity of the respondents. Besides, the data presented were aggregate and not individual, strengthening this research's claim of privacy and confidentiality.
- **Informed Consent.** The researcher informed the respondents about the nature of their involvement and the purpose of the study. Then, they were required to sign the Informed Consent Form (ICF). Before signing, the researcher allowed the respondents to read the ICF's content and ask questions. The researcher also explained the ICF to the respondents to clarify the items. The signing of the ICF happened before accomplishing the survey forms.
- **Recruitment.** The researcher wrote a letter to the Provincial Director. Then, he sent other letters to the provincial commanders conveying his intention of making their police precinct the study's locales. Fortunately, the regional commanders helped the researcher distribute and retrieve the survey questionnaires, as it was challenging to gather the police personnel due to their hectic schedules.
- **Risks.** Nothing was incriminating in the study and never involved any dangers for the researcher and the police personnel. Aside from the observance of privacy and confidentiality, no item in the survey instrument was self-incriminating. Therefore, the respondents felt relaxed in accomplishing the questionnaire.
- **Benefits.** The study would not yield a particular advantage for each police personnel but a generalized benefit for the entire organization, and the police personnel would enjoy indirect benefits. In other words, once the result of this study pinpoints the determinants of job engagement, the agency may use it in designing a doable framework for the job engagement of their personnel. In effect, the personnel may manifest a better job performance, yielding economic (financial) and social (status, work promotion) benefits.
- **Plagiarism.** The researcher knows that plagiarism is a criminal offense. It is punishable by the Intellectual Property Code and the Cybercrime Prevention Act. The latter carries a penalty that is a degree higher than the former. To avoid plagiarism, the researcher ensured that authors whose works he cited in this study got credited through proper attribution in in-text citations and the list of references. Also, the *Turnitin software* helped avert the incidence of plagiarism by detecting the similarity index of his work with other sources of information.
- **Fabrication.** Like plagiarism, the manufacture of research data is also severe misconduct. In this study, the researcher used only the data collected using the prescribed instrument of the study. Also, the researcher made conclusions and recommendations based on the study's findings.
- **Falsification.** The researcher knows that falsifying research data is an offense comparable to data fabrication and plagiarism. These offenses are dealt with by law. Therefore, to prevent such crimes, the researcher upheld the integrity of the data by accurately collecting and presenting them. No manipulation of research materials, processes, changing or omitting data or results happened in this research. Also, to reiterate, this study used the APA format in attributing works in the list of references.
- **Conflict of Interest.** The researcher has no conflict of interest with the study or the PNP agency. Additionally, the researcher did not receive outside funding for this research—this paper intended to satisfy a requirement for a post-graduate degree. Therefore, no external force can influence the researcher's judgment but based his conclusions solely on the analysis of the collected data.
- **Deceit.** Honesty is the foremost requirement in research. Almost all of the assessment points in the ethical considerations point to honesty. This study is free from any forms of deceit, from the recruitment of respondents to the data collection and analysis. The researcher was honest in disclosing to the respondents the purpose of the study. Revealing the purpose of the study is the first step in upholding the integrity of research, which the researcher did before the actual conduct of the study to get the respondents' voluntary participation.

- ***Permission from Organization/Location.*** Before starting the study, the researcher wrote a permission letter to the provincial director and each provincial police office. Then, the researcher waited for the approval of the letter before proceeding with data gathering.
- ***Authorship.*** Regarding authorship, the researcher is the first author in this study, and the adviser is the second author. The same is true in the paper's publication; the adviser would also share the credit. Moreover, the researcher has appended his CV to the final manuscript.

CHAPTER 3

RESULTS

Presented in this chapter are the presentation and analyses of data. The discussions follow the sequence based on the research objectives and the statistical results—first, the results of the descriptive statistics; second, the correlation test; third, the outcome of the multiple regression analysis; fourth, The coefficient of determination; and fifth, the result of the Structural Equation Modeling.

A. Political Skills, Resilience at Work, Public Service Motivation, and Job Engagement of Police Personnel in Region 11

Shown in Table 1 is the data on political skills. The overall high mean score was 4.90, with a standard deviation of .36. The very high mean score suggests that the respondents always exhibited political skills. Subsequently, the 0.36 standard deviation signified the homogeneity of responses in each survey item, resulting in a small standard score of 0.36. This standard score conveys that the data falls within the normal curve, the expected data. In other words, the responses in the survey were the expected answers. When responses are varied, the standard score is more prominent, indicating the data dispersal away from the mean, meaning the answers given in the survey were not the expected (norm) responses. A standard score (Z-score) of 1.0 and above indicates one or two standard deviations away from the mean, revealing the variances in the answers. The bigger the Z-score, the farther it is away from the norm.

In Table 1 is shown that all mean scores were very high, and the standard scores are below 1.0, denoting uniformity of responses in the statements in the survey. For example, networking ability had a mean score of 4.89, with a 0.52 standard deviation. Interpersonal influence had 4.91, social astuteness had 4.87, and apparent sincerity had 4.92. They have standard scores of 0.70, 0.33, and 0.69, respectively. The appendices section of this paper displays all the specific data per table, with questions also.

The survey statements on networking ability are the following: *spending a lot of time and effort at work networking with others, being good at building relationships with influential people at work, developing an extensive network of colleagues and associates at work for support, knowing many people at work, spending much time at work developing connections, and being good at using links and network to make things happen at work.* Respondents gave very high ratings to all these statements.

Moreover, the statements on interpersonal influence include: *being able to make most people feel comfortable and at ease, being able to communicate efficiently and effectively with others, being easy to develop a good rapport with most people, and being good at getting people to like them.* Likewise, all statements got very high ratings.

For social astuteness, these are the statements: *understanding people very well, being particularly good at sensing the motivations and hidden agendas of others, having good intuition or savvy about how to present self to others, instinctively knowing the right things to say or do to influence others and pays close attention to people's facial expressions.* As a result, the respondents rated these statements very highly.

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Networking Ability	0.52	4.89	Very high
Interpersonal Influence	0.70	4.91	Very high
Social Astuteness	0.33	4.87	Very high
Apparent Sincerity	0.69	4.92	Very high
Overall	0.36	4.90	Very high

Table 1: Level of Political Skills of the Police Personnel in Region 11

Finally, the statements on apparent sincerity that respondents gave very high ratings are the following: *trying to be genuine in what to say and do, getting people to believe in the honesty of what they say and do, trying to show a genuine interest in other people, and paying close attention to people's facial expressions.*

The very high rating respondents gave to these statements indicates that they always do all these things, assuring the PNP in Region 11 of their excellent *networking ability, interpersonal skills, social astuteness, and apparent sincerity.*

In Table 2 is shown the data on resilience at work. The overall mean score is *very high* at 4.89, with a standard deviation of 0.22. In the table is shown that all indicators got very high mean scores, indicating that respondents consistently demonstrate resilience in the following manner: authentic living, finding a calling, maintaining perspective, managing stress, building social connections, and staying healthy.

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Authentic Living	0.33	4.85	Very high
Finding Calling	0.33	4.86	Very high
Maintaining Perspective	0.30	4.89	Very high
Managing Stress	0.28	4.90	Very high
Building Social Connections	0.28	4.90	Very high
Staying Healthy	0.25	4.93	Very high
Overall	0.22	4.89	Very high

Table 2: Level of Resilience at Work of the Police Personnel in Region 11

Observing the individual results, the standard scores ranged from 0.25 to 0.33 indicating that almost all respondents gave the same answers in the survey because of the small standard scores. Therefore, these are the gist of the statements in the survey.

For example, under authentic living are the following: *having core values for work-life, knowing personal strengths and using them regularly at work, and changing moods when needed.* Under finding a calling, these are the statements: *work helps them find a life's sense of purpose, and a workplace is where they feel they belong and appreciate their work environment.* Maintaining perspective, *they are not frightened by anything at work and are not affected by negative people at work.*

Additionally, they managed stress by taking breaks, finding ways to relax, and dealing with the challenges at work. They were careful that their work did not dominate their personal life. In building social connections, they often ask for feedback to improve performance. They have friends at work who support them and a solid and reliable network of supportive colleagues. Most importantly, they stayed healthy by having a good level of physical fitness and being careful about their diet and eating habits.

In Table 3 is presented the respondents' data on *public service motivation*. Again, all indicators got very high mean scores, resulting in a very high mean score of 4.88, with a standard deviation of 0.27. As explained earlier, the small standard scores mean that the data are close to the mean. Self-sacrifice has a very high level, as evidenced by a mean score of 4.88, which means that the respondents are ready to make enormous sacrifices for the good of society. They believe in putting duty before themselves. They think serving other citizens would give them a good feeling.

Additionally, attraction to policymaking obtained a 4.90 mean score, with a standard deviation of 0.27. The result conveys that the respondents always believe that sharing their views with the public appeals to them. Moreover, seeing people benefiting from the programs gives them great satisfaction. Also, they are interested in making and participating in public programs that are beneficial to the community, as they consider these programs meaningful public service and civic duties. Finally, they perform public service with compassion (M=4.87; SD=0.36).

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Self-sacrifice	0.32	4.88	Very high
Attraction to Policy Making	0.27	4.90	Very high
Compassion	0.36	4.87	Very high
Overall	0.27	4.88	Very high

Table 3: Level of Public Service Motivation of the Police Personnel in Region 11

For instance, they always thought of dependence on one another, feeling sympathetic to the plight of the underprivileged, and making a difference in society means more than personal achievements.

In Table 4 is conveyed the data on the job engagement of the police personnel in Region 11. Again, all three indicators got very high scores: Cognitive engagement (M=4.90; SD 0.29), emotional engagement (M=4.91; SD=0.27), and physical engagement (M=4.91; SD=0.29). The data illustrate that the respondents have always manifested the behaviors and actions stipulated under job engagement. That, under the cognitive dimension, their minds are always full of ideas about their work. Wherever they are, things often happen that remind them of their work, making their minds engaged fully and focused on their work.

Moreover, under emotional engagement, they always feel delighted about what they do at work, eager to work, happy to carry responsibilities at work, feel good about work, have enthusiasm for work, and have a sense of gratification with work performance. Finally, physically, they always have high energy and stamina at work.

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Cognitive Engagement Dimension	0.29	4.90	Very high
Emotional Engagement Dimension	0.27	4.91	Very high
Physical Engagement Dimension	0.29	4.91	Very high
Overall	0.25	4.90	Very high

Table 4: Level of Job Engagement of Police Personnel in Region XI

In Table 5 is contained the summary results of the levels of political skills (M=4.90; SD=0.36), resilience at work (M=4.89; SD=0.22), public service motivation (M=4.88; SD=0.27), and job engagement (M=4.90; SD=0.25) of police personnel in Region 11. The table presents an overall high level of both the exogenous and endogenous variables. All standard deviations are below 1.0, which describes the concentration of data around the mean, conveying almost the same responses in the survey.

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Political Skills	0.36	4.90	Very high
Resilience at Work	0.22	4.89	Very high
Public Service Motivation	0.27	4.88	Very high
Job Engagement	0.25	4.90	Very high

Table 5: Summary Table of the Levels of Political Skills, Resilience at Work, Public Service Motivation and Job Engagement of Police Personnel in Region 11

B. Relationship between the Exogenous and Endogenous Latent Variables

In Table 6 is displayed the result of the correlation test between the exogenous variables: political skills, resilience, public service motivation, and job engagement. The value $p < 0.05$ is the basis of the significance level. It is shown in the table that all tests are significant: thus successfully rejecting the null hypothesis. The result means that all exogenous variables have substantial relationships with job engagement.

Moreover, the 2-tailed test showed a significant relationship, denoting that the mean scores are significant in the distribution's upper and lower tails. The function of a 2-tailed test is to establish whether the mean is significantly greater than X and lower than X, which would result in a p-value of less than 0.05. Therefore, significant. Table 5 shows that all tests are significant. Political skills, resilience, and public service motivation significantly correlate with job engagement.

The inference is that job engagement would increase when these three exogenous variables increase. The coefficient of correlation revealed a significant relationship for all exogenous variables: between political skills and job engagement ($r = .517, p < .000$), resilience and job engagement ($r = .737, p < .000$), and public service motivation and job engagement ($r = .768, p < .000$). The relationship is also positive. The strong and positive correlation signifies that the change in the exogenous variable can significantly positively impact the endogenous variable. For example, the increase in political skills can moderately increase job engagement.

Exogenous Variables	Job Engagement (endogenous variable)			
	Cognitive Engagement	Emotional Engagement	Cognitive Engagement	Overall
Political Skills	.461** .000	.437** .000	.495** .000	.517** .000
Resilience	.643** .000	.644** .000	.702** .000	.737** .000
Public Service Motivation	.683** .000	.663** .000	.725** .000	.768** .000

Table 6: Significant Relationship between the Exogenous Latent and Endogenous Latent Variables

** The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

* The correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

C. Influence of the Exogenous Latent Variables on Job Engagement

Table 7 presents the regression analysis that tested the influence of the exogenous variables on job engagement. As revealed in the data, all three exogenous variables significantly influence job engagement, namely; political skills, resilience, and public service motivation. The combined influence of political skills, resilience at work, and public service motivation on job engagement is 67.8% ($\Delta R=.678$), implying that 32.2% of the job engagement of the police personnel in Region 11 is because of other factors beyond the scope of this study. However, taking the influence of each exogenous variable on job engagement into consideration, the coefficient of determination shows that political skills, resilience, and public service motivation can each influence job .

Exogenous Variables	Job Performance			
	B	β	t	Sig.
Constant	.421		2.663	.008
Political Skill	.086	.123	3.695	.000
Resilience	.474	.358	8.828	.000
Public Service Motivation	.436	.460	11.366	.000
	R	.825		
	R ²	.681		
	ΔR	.678		
	F	282.643		
	ρ	.000		

Table 7: Significant Influence of the Exogenous Latent Variables on Job Engagement

engagement by 68.1 percent ($R^2=.681$). As stated earlier, the combined influence of the three exogenous variables on job engagement is 67.8%. This change in the value of R^2 is due to adding other variables to the equation. R^2 changes for each added variable; the more variables added, the lesser the coefficient of determination (R^2). The individual result per beta coefficient showed that the topmost exogenous variable influencing job engagement is resilience ($B=.474$, $p=.000$). Next is public service motivation, with a beta coefficient of .436 at the p -value. 000. Last is political skills ($B=.086$, $p=.000$).

Finally, the F -value of 282.643 with $p=.000$ indicates the regression model's statistically significant predictive capability. To reiterate, resilience best influences job engagement. Therefore, for every change in the strength of the police personnel in Region XI, the same degree of transformation happens in their job engagement.

D. Best Fit Structural Model for Job Performance

This portion establishes the best fit model for job engagement. Table 8 contains the goodness of fit measures of the five generated models, following these criteria: a p -value greater than 0.05. A Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom (CNIM/DF) between 0 and 2. A value greater than .95 for the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Normed Fit Index (NFI), and Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI). The Root Means Square of Error Approximation (RMSEA) of less than 0.05. Finally, the P of Close Fit (P-close) should be greater than 0.05. In Table 8, only Model 5 has met the goodness of fit criteria. The models follow after Table 8 for better appreciation.

Model	P-value (>0.05)	CMIN / DF (0<value<2)	GFI (>0.95)	CFI (>0.95)	NFI (>0.95)	TLI (>0.95)	RMSEA (<0.05)	P-close (>0.05)
1	.000	7.391	.817	.748	.722	.696	.127	.000
2	.000	6.522	.841	.787	.760	.737	.118	.000
3	.000	5.430	.857	.829	.800	.789	.105	.000
4	.000	5.755	.845	.815	.786	.774	.109	.000
5	.222	1.220	.987	.996	.980	.992	.023	.944

Table 8: Summary of Goodness of Fit Measures of the Five Generated Models

Fig. 3: Generated Diagram designated as Model 1

Legend:

- NA – networking ability
- II – interpersonal influence
- SA – social astuteness
- HS – apparent sincerity
- LA – living authentically
- FC – finding calling
- MP – maintaining perspective
- MS – managing stress
- BC – building social connections
- SH – studying healthy
- SS – self-sacrifice
- AM – attraction to policymaking
- CO – compassion
- CED – cognitive engagement dimension
- EED – emotional engagement dimension
- PED – physical engagement dimension

Fig. 4: Generated Diagram designated as Model 2

Legend:

- | | | |
|-------------------------------------|---|---|
| <i>NA – networking ability</i> | <i>MP – maintaining perspective</i> | <i>AM – attraction to policymaking</i> |
| <i>II – interpersonal influence</i> | <i>MS – managing stress</i> | <i>CO – compassion</i> |
| <i>SA – social astuteness</i> | <i>BC – building social connections</i> | <i>CED – cognitive engagement dimension</i> |
| <i>HS – apparent sincerity</i> | <i>SH – studying healthy</i> | <i>EED – emotional engagement dimension</i> |
| <i>LA – living authentically</i> | <i>SS – self-sacrifice</i> | <i>PED – physical engagement dimension</i> |
| <i>FC – finding calling</i> | | |

Fig. 5: Generated Diagram designated as Model 3

Legend:

- | | | |
|-------------------------------------|---|---|
| <i>NA – networking ability</i> | <i>MP – maintaining perspective</i> | <i>AM – attraction to policymaking</i> |
| <i>II – interpersonal influence</i> | <i>MS – managing stress</i> | <i>CO – compassion</i> |
| <i>SA – social astuteness</i> | <i>BC – building social connections</i> | <i>CED – cognitive engagement dimension</i> |
| <i>HS – apparent sincerity</i> | <i>SH – studying healthy</i> | <i>EED – emotional engagement dimension</i> |
| <i>LA – living authentically</i> | <i>SS – self-sacrifice</i> | <i>PED – physical engagement dimension</i> |
| <i>FC – finding calling</i> | | |

Fig. 6: Generated Diagram designated as Model 4

Legend:

- | | | |
|------------------------------|----------------------------------|--------------------------------------|
| NA – networking ability | MP – maintaining perspective | AM – attraction to policymaking |
| II – interpersonal influence | MS – managing stress | CO – compassion |
| SA – social astuteness | BC – building social connections | CED – cognitive engagement dimension |
| HS – apparent sincerity | SH – studying healthy | EED – emotional engagement dimension |
| LA – living authentically | SS – self-sacrifice | PED – physical engagement dimension |
| FC – finding calling | | |

Fig. 7: The Best-Fit Structural Model for Job Performance

Legend:

- | | | |
|-------------------------------------|---|---|
| <i>NA – networking ability</i> | <i>MP – maintaining perspective</i> | <i>AM – attraction to policymaking</i> |
| <i>II – interpersonal influence</i> | <i>MS – managing stress</i> | <i>CO – compassion</i> |
| <i>SA – social astuteness</i> | <i>BC – building social connections</i> | <i>CED – cognitive engagement dimension</i> |
| <i>HS – apparent sincerity</i> | <i>SH – studying healthy</i> | <i>EED – emotional engagement dimension</i> |
| <i>LA – living authentically</i> | <i>SS – self-sacrifice</i> | <i>PED – physical engagement dimension</i> |
| <i>FC – finding calling</i> | | |

In Figure 7 above is shown the best fit model in the study, designated as Model 5, for job performance. All values fit the criterion indices of the goodness of fit measures in Tables 8 and 9. The model shows the exogenous latent variables and manifest variables. The exogenous latent variable means are not directly observable and measured only through their manifest variables (or indicators). For example, in the model below, all three exogenous variables predict job engagement.

In the model, political skills can influence public service motivation and job engagement through manifest variables such as networking ability (NA), social astuteness (SA), interpersonal influence (II), and apparent sincerity (AS). On the other hand, public service motivation can also influence job engagement through its manifest variables: self-sacrifice (SS), attraction to policymaking (AP), and compassion (CO). Finally, resilience can influence public service motivation and job engagement through manifest variables: living authentically (LA), finding a calling (FC), maintaining perspective (MP), managing stress (MS), building social connections (BC), and studying healthy (SH).

In Table 9 are contained the best-fit model values (see Figure 7, Model 5) that match all the goodness of fit measures. Further, in Table 10 are displayed the independent variables' direct, indirect, and total effects on job engagement in the best-fit model (Figure 7). Political skill has an 86.3% full effect on job engagement. Resilience has a 79.4% effect on job engagement, while public service motivation has a 52.7% direct effect on job engagement. In this data, public service motivation most impacts job engagement.

INDEX	CRITERION	MODEL FIT VALUE
P-value	> 0.05	.359
CMIN/DF	0 < value < 2	1.046
GFI	> 0.95	.970
CFI	> 0.95	.999
NFI	> 0.95	.971
TLI	> 0.95	.998
RMSEA	< 0.05	.011
P-Close	> 0.05	1.000

Table 9: Values obtained for the Best-Fit Model

Legend:

CMIN/DF - Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom

TLI - Tucker-Lewis Index

GFI - Goodness of Fit Index

P-close- P of Close Fit

CFI - Comparative Fit Index

NFI - Normed Fit Index

RMSEA - Root Means Square of Error Approximation

Variables	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	Total Effect
Political Skill	.171	.692	.863
Resilience	.289	.505	.794
Public Service Motivation	.527	-	.527

Table 10: Direct and Indirect Effects of the Independent Variables on Job Engagement of Best Fit Model

Moreover, Table 11 presents the regression weights in generated best fit model. The asterisks (***) indicate that the manifest variables of the latent exogenous variables are predictors of job performance. The regression results revealed that political skills, resilience at work, and public service motivation could influence job engagement. Finally, table 11 is the tabular presentation of Figure 7, the best-fit model for job performance.

			Estimate	SE.	Beta	CR.	P-value
Resilience	<---	Political_Skill	.719	.126	.772	5.717	***
Public_Service_Motivation	<---	Political_Skill	.229	.105	.190	2.171	.030
Public_Service_Motivation	<---	Resilience	.958	.114	.740	8.387	***
Job_Engagement	<---	Political_Skill	.171	.081	.156	2.102	.036
Job_Engagement	<---	Resilience	.289	.130	.245	2.218	.027
Job_Engagement	<---	Public_Service_Motivation	.527	.108	.578	4.883	***
HS	<---	Political_Skill	1.000		.323		
SA	<---	Political_Skill	1.260	.215	.851	5.876	***
II	<---	Political_Skill	1.139	.245	.364	4.658	***
NA	<---	Political_Skill	1.150	.218	.489	5.274	***
CO	<---	Public_Service_Motivation	1.000		.745		
AM	<---	Public_Service_Motivation	.836	.051	.825	16.331	***
SS	<---	Public_Service_Motivation	.834	.061	.700	13.738	***
SH	<---	Resilience	1.000		.829		
BC	<---	Resilience	1.010	.061	.740	16.463	***
MS	<---	Resilience	1.071	.059	.799	18.158	***
MP	<---	Resilience	1.046	.067	.719	15.699	***
FC	<---	Resilience	1.045	.082	.656	12.752	***
LA	<---	Resilience	.764	.083	.482	9.181	***
CED	<---	Job_Engagement	1.000		.839		
EED	<---	Job_Engagement	.882	.046	.805	19.224	***
PED	<---	Job_Engagement	1.053	.047	.893	22.566	***

Table 11: Estimates of Variable Regression Weights in Generated Best Fit Model

Legend:

NA – networking ability

II – interpersonal influence

SA – social astuteness

HS – apparent sincerity

LA – living authentically

FC – finding calling

MP – maintaining perspective

MS – managing stress

BC – building social connections

SH – studying healthy

SS – self-sacrifice

AM – attraction to policymaking

CO – compassion

CED – cognitive engagement dimension

EED – emotional engagement dimension

PED – physical engagement dimension

CHAPTER 4

DISCUSSION

In this chapter are contained the analyses of the results presented in Chapter 3 of this paper. The order of discussion follows the same sequence made in the presentation of the results.

A. Political Skills, Resilience at Work, Public Service Motivation, and Job Engagement of Police Personnel in Region 11

Overall, the results showed very high political skills, resilience at work, public service motivation, and job engagement, suggesting that police personnel have outstanding networking ability, interpersonal influence, social astuteness, and apparent sincerity. Likewise, the result indicates that they also have excellent work resilience, as evidenced by very high ratings in authentic living, finding a calling, maintaining perspective, managing stress, building social connections, and staying healthy. Furthermore, the results showed that police personnel have high public service motivation concerning self-sacrifice, attraction to policymaking, and compassion. They also have very high cognitive, emotional, and physical job engagements.

The varying socio-political environment gives the police contemporary stress that requires political skills to combat effectively (Saunders, Kotzias, & Ramchand, 2019). More often, police are victims of mob violence, caught in the crossfire between political leaders and the people, putting the lives of police and other people in danger (Marenin, 2018). Moreover, political skills are necessary for advancing a career at an individual level. Without it, the individual cannot leverage career development (Lee, Yun, & Kim, 2019).

Because of the contemporary stress that the police face, they have to have resilience at work to withstand whatever challenges, their high-level strength at work could help them surmount every difficulty in the job. Still, to have stability, police personnel should have proper training because various factors combined may cause police resilience to weaken (Chitra & Karunanidhi, 2021). Nevertheless, on the other hand, with solid strength at work, police can face various challenges and difficulties, like trauma, threats, and tragedies (Krause & Halkitis, 2020).

Studies have shown that high-level public service motivation encourages accountability among employees. This claim may also be valid among police personnel, thus, resulting in better job performance (Schwarz, Eva, & Newman, 2020). In addition, Breugh, Ritz, and Alfes (2018) observed that employees with high-level motivation to serve the public showed more job satisfaction, and their satisfaction was more stable than those with lower PSM. As government employees, these findings strengthen public service motivation among police personnel to find inspiration, happiness, and accountability in doing their job. If police personnel demonstrate these behaviors in their work, people will see their confidence and cooperate with the police, just as they did in other professions (Zhang, Wang, Shi, Liu, Huang, Wang, & Sun, 2021).

Finally, job engagement was found very high among the police personnel. According to Brunetto et al. (2020), job engagement affects the work of the police. Because of this, management support becomes necessary. Therefore, the authors proposed how management could support the police: by training police managers to promote widespread police engagement and by modifying the performance indicators of police managers in line with better police engagement. Nevertheless, research shows that the intrinsic values of the police personnel can drive them to engage harder for better work outcomes (Basinska & Dãderman, 2019). Hence, it becomes vital that police personnel identify their values and make them meaningful towards better job engagement.

B. Relationship of Political Skills, Resilience at Work, Public Service Motivation and Job Performance

This study found a significant, positive, and solid relationship between political skills, resilience at work, public service motivation, and job engagement. Therefore, this study affirms Basit's (2020) finding that political skills impact job performance. Furthermore, a study even found that political skills can mitigate job dissatisfaction, thus, encouraging employees to be more engaged in their jobs and to perform better (De Clercq, Haq, Azeem, & Ahmad, 2019).

Additionally, the result affirms the research finding on the positive correlation between resilience at work and job performance (Kašpárková, Vaculík, Procházka, & Schaufeli, 2018). If individual strength positively impacts job performance, it does more so with team resilience (McEwen & Boyd, 2018), suggesting cohesiveness among police personnel to attain beyond expectations of job performance.

Moreover, public service motivation (PSM) and job engagement are significantly correlated. Also, higher PSM congruently impacts public service engagements (Schwarz, Eva, & Newman, 2020). In other words, the more police personnel are motivated to serve, the more they engage in their job, making PSM a driver for job performance. Another study found a substantial impact of PSM on job performance in the government sector, especially if job resources are available (Boyd, Nowell, Yang, & Hano, 2018). That study revealed that as job resources increased, public service motivation increased, and employees became emotionally committed to the organization (Rajagukguk & Desiana, 2021). Bringing that finding into this study would mean that the police would be highly motivated to work when resources are available. The result is a more substantial commitment to their work and the organization.

C. Influence of Political Skills, Resilience at Work and Public Service Motivation on Job Performance

The regression results showed a remarkable influence of the exogenous variables (*political skills, resilience at work, and public service motivation*) on the endogenous variable (*job performance*). This finding can reinforce previous results. For example, research shows that political skills influence the mitigation of employees' role ambiguity, although not role overload, which helps employees thrive in the organization (Cullen, Gerbasi, & Chrobot-Mason, 2018). Also, political skills influence both partial mediation and moderation between leadership and innovative behavior (Zhou & Wu, 2018) in that employees' affective and attributional tendencies become stimuli of leaders in their leadership style (Russell, Steffensen, Ellen III, et al., 2018).

Research also shows that resilience at work can influence team performance and develop adaptability (McEwen & Boyd, 2018). This situation happens in almost all working arenas, even in the health care profession (Walpita & Arambepola, 2020). Interestingly, resilient workers have better job performance, primarily when satisfied and engaged (Kašpárková, Vaculík, Procházka, & Schaufeli, 2018).

Additionally, public service motivation influences public sector employees' perception, resulting in higher job performance levels and organizational identification (Miao, Newman, Schwarz, & Cooper, 2018; Miao, Eva, Newman, & Schwarz, 2019). The authors concluded the importance of public service motivation in enhancing job performance and innovative behavior (Miao, Newman, Schwarz, & Cooper, 2018; Van Loon, Kjeldsen, Andersen, Vandenabeele, & Leisink, 2018). This result has implications for public sector employment.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION

Based on the results, the study concludes that: the levels of political skills, resilience at work, public service motivation, and job engagement of police personnel in Region 11 are very high. In addition, there is a significant, positive, and solid relationship between political skills (PS), resilience at work (RaW), public service motivation (PSM), and job engagement (JE). There is a significant influence of PS, RaW, and PSM on JE. The combined effect of PS, RaW, and PSM on job engagement is 67.8%. Individually, they can influence JE at 68.1 percent. Political skills, resilience at work, and public service motivation are predictors of job engagement with their respective manifest variables. Essentially, the findings of this study signify that there is a model for job performance. This model affirms the Signaling Theory (Spence, 1974), Resilience Theory (Garmezy, 1991), and the Moral Foundations Theory (Graham, Haidt, Koleva, Motyl, Iyer, Wojcik, & Ditto, 2013) used as foundations of this study.

A. Recommendations

These are the following recommendations based on the findings and conclusion of the study. First, there may be a need to sustain the political skills, resilience at work, public service motivation, and job engagement practices of the police personnel since they have very high levels of these variables. Second, it may be essential to give each police personnel recognition and commendation for a job well done to motivate them to engage faithfully in their work. Third, the agency may encourage officers and other researchers to conduct action research within their police stations to have research-based findings to improve their work and the relationship with the community.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Abushinov, S. (2021). Swedish Cultural Influence on the Networking Ability of Arabic Immigrant Entrepreneurs.
- [2.] Adomako, S., Danso, A., Boso, N., & Narteh, B. (2018). Entrepreneurial alertness and new venture performance: Facilitating roles of networking capability. *International Small Business Journal*, 36(5), 453-472.
- [3.] Afsar, B., Umrani, W. A., & Khan, A. (2019). The impact of perceived calling on work outcomes in a nursing context: The role of career commitment and living one's calling. *Journal of Applied Biobehavioral Research*, 24(1), e12154.
- [4.] Alramdhan, S. A., & Sattar, H. S. A. (2021). The Impact of Political Skills on Strategic Decision-Making for Senior Leaders-Directorates of Education. *Review of International Geographical Education Online*, 11(12).
- [5.] Andersen, J. P., Papazoglou, K., & Collins, P. (2018). Association of authoritarianism, compassion fatigue, and compassion satisfaction among police officers in North America: an exploration. *International Journal of Criminal Justice Sciences*, 13(2), 405-419.
- [6.] Antony, M. R. (2018). The paradigm shift in employee engagement—A critical analysis on the drivers of employee engagement. *International Journal of Information, Business, and Management*, 10(2), 32-46.
- [7.] Barkacs, C. (2021, June 16). *4 ways to improve your political skill on the path to power | Psychology Today Singapore*. [www.psychologytoday.com. https://www.psychologytoday.com/sg/blog/power-and-influence/202106/4ways-improve-your-political-skill-the-path-power](https://www.psychologytoday.com/sg/blog/power-and-influence/202106/4ways-improve-your-political-skill-the-path-power)
- [8.] Basinska, B. A., & Dåderman, A. M. (2019). Work values of police officers and their relationship with job burnout and work engagement. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 442.
- [9.] Basit, A. A. (2019). Examining how respectful engagement affects task performance and affective organizational commitment: The role of job engagement. *Personnel Review*.
- [10.] Basit, A. A. (2020). How does political skill lead to job and organization engagement? Role of self-evaluations. *Journal of Management Development*.
- [11.] Bélanger, J. J., Schumpe, B. M., Menon, B., Ng, J., Nociti, N., Zeigler-Hill, V., & Shackelford, T. K. (2018). Self-sacrifice for a cause: a review and an integrative model. *V. Zeigler-Hill & TK Shackelford, The sage handbook of personality and individual differences*, 465-485.
- [12.] Bernecker, K., & Becker, D. (2021). Beyond self-control: mechanisms of hedonic goal pursuit and its relevance for well-being. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 47(4), 627-642.
- [13.] Bhattarai, G. (2022). Perception of Organizational Politics and Career Satisfaction: Mediating Role of Networking Ability and Self-promotion Behavior. *Business Perspectives and Research*, 22785337211070379.
- [14.] Blickle, G., Frieder, R. E., & Ferris, G. R. (2018). Political skill. In D. S. Ones, N. Anderson, C. Viswesvaran, & H. K. Sinangil (Eds.), *The SAGE handbook of industrial, work & organizational psychology: Personnel psychology and employee performance*, 299–319.
- [15.] Bongers, S., Forré, P., Peters, J., & Mooij, J. M. (2021). Foundations of structural causal models with cycles and latent variables. *The Annals of Statistics*, 49(5), 2885-2915.
- [16.] Bonanno, G. A. (2021). The resilience paradox. *European Journal of Psychotraumatology*, 12(1), 1942642.
- [17.] Borst, R. T., Krueger, P. M., & Lako, C. J. (2019). Exploring the Job Demands– Resources Model of Work Engagement in Government: Bringing in a Psychological Perspective. *Review of Public Personnel Administration*, 39(3), 372–397. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734371X17729870>

- [18.] Bostanci, A. B. (2020). The Relationship between Teachers' Political Skills and Work Engagement. *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*, 8(4), 53. <https://doi.org/10.7575/aiac.ijels.v.8n.4p.53>
- [19.] Boyd, N., Nowell, B., Yang, Z., & Hano, M. C. (2018). Sense of community, sense of community responsibility, and public service motivation as predictors of employee well-being and engagement in public service organizations. *The American Review of Public Administration*, 48(5), 428443.
- [20.] Breugh, J., Ritz, A., & Alfes, K. (2018). Work motivation and public service motivation: disentangling varieties of motivation and job satisfaction. *Public Management Review*, 20(10), 1423-1443.
- [21.] Brey, P. (2018). The strategic role of technology in a good society. *Technology in society*, 52(C), 39-45.
- [22.] Brouer, R. L., Chiu, C. Y. C., & Wang, L. (2016). Political skill dimensions and transformational leadership in China. *Journal of managerial psychology*.
- [23.] Brunetto, Y., Farr-Wharton, B., Farr-Wharton, R., Shacklock, K., Azzopardi, J., Saccon, C., & Shriberg, A. (2020). Comparing the impact of management support on police officers' perceptions of discretionary power and engagement: Australia, USA, and Malta. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 31(6), 738-759.
- [24.] Burnett, M. E., Sheard, I., & St Clair-Thompson, H. (2020). The prevalence of compassion fatigue, compassion satisfaction, perceived stress, their relationships with mental toughness, individual differences, and a number of self-care actions in a UK police force. *Police Practice and Research*, 21(4), 383-400.
- [25.] Cabalza, D. (2018, June 16). *2 police officers fired for poor performance*. INQUIRER.net. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1001281/2-police-officers-fired-for-poor-performance>
- [26.] Cabato, R. (2018, June 13). *24 town police chiefs relieved for "low performance" in anti-illegal drugs operations*. <https://www.cnnphilippines.com/news/2018/06/13/24-town-police-relieved-low-performance-drug-operations.html>
- [27.] Cao, X., & Chen, L. (2020). The impact of empathy on work engagement in hemodialysis nurses: The mediating role of resilience. *Japan Journal of Nursing Science*, 17(1). <https://doi.org/10.1111/jjns.12284>
- [28.] Castillo De Mesa, J., Gómez Jacinto, L., López Peláez, A., & Palma García, M. D. L. O. (2019). Building relationships on social networking sites from a social work approach. *Journal of social work practice*, 33(2), 201-215.
- [29.] Cavanaugh, R. (2021). Ashley Grossman: finding a calling in neuroendocrinology. *The Lancet Diabetes & Endocrinology*, 9(9), 560.
- [30.] Chan, X. W., Kalliath, T., & Cheng, D. (2020). When the boss is blue: Examining the effects of supervisors' negative emotions on subordinates' cognitive work engagement and family undermining. *Personnel Review*.
- [31.] Chanana, K. (2020). Women and leadership: Strategies of gender inclusion in institutions of higher education in India. In *Strategies for Supporting Inclusion and Diversity in the Academy* (pp. 141-162). Palgrave Macmillan, Cham.
- [32.] Chen, H., Richard, O. C., Boncoeur, O. D., & Ford Jr, D. L. (2020). Work engagement, emotional exhaustion, and counterproductive work behavior. *Journal of Business Research*, 114, 30-41.
- [33.] Chen, J., May, D. R., Schwoerer, C. E., & Augelli, B. (2018). Exploring the boundaries of career calling: The moderating roles of procedural justice and psychological safety. *Journal of Career Development*, 45(2), 103-116.
- [34.] Chen, S., & Murphy, D. (2019). The mediating role of authenticity on mindfulness and wellbeing: a cross-cultural analysis. *Asia Pacific Journal of Counselling and Psychotherapy*, 10(1), 40-55.
- [35.] Chitra, T., & Karunanidhi, S. (2021). The impact of resilience training on occupational stress, resilience, job satisfaction, and psychological wellbeing of female police officers. *Journal of Police and Criminal Psychology*, 36(1), 8-23.

- [36.] Christensen, R. K., Paarlberg, L., & Perry, J. L. (2017). Public service motivation research: Lessons for practice. *Public Administration Review*, 77(4), 529-542.
- [37.] Cieślak, I., Kielan, A., Olejniczak, D., Panczyk, M., Jaworski, M., Gałązkowski, R., ... & Mikos, M. (2020). Stress at work: The case of municipal police officers. *Work*, 65(1), 145-152.
- [38.] Civelek, M. E. (2018). Essentials of structural equation modeling. *Essentials of Structural Equation Modeling (2018)*.
- [39.] Converse, B. A., Juarez, L., & Hennecke, M. (2019). Self-control and the reasons behind our goals. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 116(5), 860.
- [40.] Cooke, F. L., Cooper, B., Bartram, T., Wang, J., & Mei, H. (2019). Mapping the relationships between high-performance work systems, employee resilience and engagement: a study of the banking industry in China. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 30(8), 1239–1260. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2015.1137618>
- [41.] Courpasson, D., & Monties, V. (2017). “I am my body”. Physical selves of police officers in a changing institution. *Journal of Management Studies*, 54(1), 32-57.
- [42.] Cullen, K. L., Gerbasi, A., & Chrobot-Mason, D. (2018). Thriving in central network positions: The role of political skill. *Journal of Management*, 44(2), 682-706.
- [43.] De Clercq, D., Haq, I. U., Azeem, M. U., & Ahmad, H. N. (2019). The relationship between workplace incivility and helping behavior: roles of job dissatisfaction and political skill. *The Journal of Psychology*, 153(5), 507-527.
- [44.] Demou, E., Hale, H., & Hunt, K. (2020). Understanding the mental health and wellbeing needs of police officers and staff in Scotland. *Police Practice and research*, 21(6), 702-716.
- [45.] Deng, H., Guan, Y., Wu, C. H., Erdogan, B., Bauer, T., & Yao, X. (2018). A relational model of perceived overqualification: The moderating role of interpersonal influence on social acceptance. *Journal of Management*, 44(8), 3288-3310.
- [46.] Duffy, R. D., Douglass, R. P., Gensmer, N. P., England, J. W., & Kim, H. J. (2019). An initial examination of the work as calling theory. *Journal of counseling psychology*, 66(3), 328.
- [47.] Eldor, L., & Harpaz, I. (2016). A process model of employee engagement: The learning climate and its relationship with extra-role performance behaviors. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 37(2), 213-235.
- [48.] Englund, R., & Bucero, A. (2019). *The complete project manager: Integrating people, organizational, and technical skills*. Berrett-Koehler Publishers.
- [49.] Etilé, F., Frijters, P., Johnston, D. W., & Shields, M. A. (2021). Measuring resilience to major life events. *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*, 191, 598-619.
- [50.] Extremera, N., Mérida-López, S., Sánchez-Álvarez, N., & Quintana-Orts, C. (2018). How does emotional intelligence make one feel better at work? The mediational role of work engagement. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 15(9), 1909.
- [51.] Fan, Y., Chen, J., Shirkey, G., John, R., Wu, S. R., Park, H., & Shao, C. (2016). Applications of structural equation modeling (SEM) in ecological studies: an updated review. *Ecological Processes*, 5(1), 1-12.
- [52.] Fehr, R., Yam, K. C., and Dang, C. (2015). Moralized leadership: the construction and consequences of ethical leader perceptions. *Acad. Manage. Rev.* 40, 182–209. doi: 10.5465/amr.2013.0358
- [53.] Ferris, G. R., Treadway, D. C., Kolodinsky, R. W., Hochwarter, W. A., Kacmar, C. J., Douglas, C., & Frink, D. D. (2005). Development and validation of the political skill inventory. *Journal of Management*, 31(1), 126–152. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206304271386>
- [54.] Fletcher, J., Parker, J., Smith, J., & Robinson, D. (2020). Staying Healthy. In *Promoting the Health and Well-Being of People with Learning Disabilities* (pp. 125-138). Springer, Cham.
- [55.] Forret, M. L. (2018). 16 Networking as and Career Management Strategy. *The Oxford handbook of job loss and job search*, 275.
- [56.] Garmezy, N. (1991). Resiliency and vulnerability to adverse developmental outcomes associated with poverty. *American behavioral scientist*, 34(4), 416-430.

- [57.] Gan, K., Li, L., & Wang, Q. (2013, May). Public Service Motivation Measurement: A Test for Perry's Proposed Scale in China. In *2013 International Conference on Public Management (ICPM-2013)* (pp. 8-12). Atlantis Press.
- [58.] Gana, K., & Broc, G. (2019). *Structural equation modeling with lavaan*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [59.] Gil-Gimeno, J., & Sánchez Capdequí, C. (2021). The Persistence of Sacrifice as Self-Sacrifice and Its Contemporary Embodiment in the 9/11 Rescuers and COVID-19 Healthcare Professionals. *Religions, 12*(5), 323.
- [60.] Gillet, N., Morin, A. J., Jeoffrion, C., & Fouquereau, E. (2020). A person-centered perspective on the combined effects of global and specific levels of job engagement. *Group & Organization Management, 45*(4), 556-594.
- [61.] Gino, F., Sezer, O., & Huang, L. (2020). To be or not to be your authentic self? Catering to others' preferences hinders performance. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes, 158*, 83-100.
- [62.] Gomes, D. A. R., de Araújo, R. M. F., & Gomes, M. S. (2018). Incidence of suicide among military police officers in South Brazil: An 11-year retrospective cohort study. *Comprehensive psychiatry, 85*, 61-66.
- [63.] Grace, J. B., Scheiner, S. M., & Schoolmaster Jr, D. R. (2015). Structural equation modeling: building and evaluating causal models: Chapter 8.
- [64.] Grace, J. B., & Irvine, K. M. (2020). Scientist's guide to developing explanatory statistical models using causal analysis principles. *Ecology, 101*(4), e02962.
- [65.] Graham, J., Haidt, J., Koleva, S., Motyl, M., Iyer, R., Wojcik, S. P., & Ditto, P. H. (2013). Moral foundations theory: The pragmatic validity of moral pluralism. In *Advances in experimental social psychology* (Vol. 47, pp. 55130). Academic Press.
- [66.] Grant, H. B., Lavery, C. F., & Decarlo, J. (2019). An exploratory study of police officers: Low compassion satisfaction and compassion fatigue. *Frontiers in psychology, 2793*.
- [67.] Grimani, A., Aboagye, E., & Kwak, L. (2019). The effectiveness of workplace nutrition and physical activity interventions in improving productivity, work performance and workability: a systematic review. *BMC public health, 19*(1), 1-12.
- [68.] Guo, L. X., Liu, C. F., & Yain, Y. S. (2020). Social entrepreneur's psychological capital, political skills, social networks and new venture performance. *Frontiers in Psychology, 11*, 925.
- [69.] Gupta, M., & Shaheen, M. (2017). Impact of work engagement on turnover intention: moderation by psychological capital in India. *Business: Theory and Practice, 18*, 136-143.
- [70.] Gutierrez, J. A. V., Ilagan, J. A., Curtis, J., Aviñante, M. J. D. R., Idaewor, V. O., & Mojares, R. E. (2015). Stress Management Among Police Officers in Batangas City, Philippines. *College of Criminology Research Journal, 6*.
- [71.] Habibi, A., Mukminin, A., Riyanto, Y., Prasojo, L. D., Sulistiyo, U., Sofwan, M., & SAUDAGAR, F. (2018). Building an online community: Student teachers' perceptions on the advantages of using social networking services in a teacher education program. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education, 19*(1), 46-61.
- [72.] Haidt, J. (2013). Moral psychology for the twenty-first century. *Journal of Moral Education, 42*(3), 281-297.
- [73.] Hall, E., & Wall, K. (2019). *Research methods for understanding professional learning*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- [74.] Harari, M. B., Herst, D. E., Parola, H. R., & Carmona, B. P. (2017). Organizational correlates of public service motivation: A meta-analysis of two decades of empirical research. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory, 27*(1), 68-84.
- [75.] Hartley, J., & Manzie, S. (2020). 'It's every breath we take here': Political astuteness and ethics in civil service leadership development. *Public Money & Management, 40*(8), 569-578.
- [76.] Hartley, J., Sancino, A., Bennister, M., & Resodihardjo, S. L. (2019). Leadership for public value: Political astuteness as a conceptual link. *Public Administration, 97*(2), 239-249.

- [77.] Hasan, M. K., Hayek, M. J., Williams Jr, W. A., Pane-Haden, S., & Gelvez, M. P. M. (2020). Activist identity construction of Madam CJ Walker. *Journal of Management History*.
- [78.] Hassan, S., Prussia, G., Mahsud, R., & Yukl, G. (2018). How leader networking, external monitoring, and representing are relevant for effective leadership. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*.
- [79.] Hassanian-Moghaddam, H., Zamani, N., & Kolahi, A. A. (2020). COVID-19 pandemic, healthcare providers' contamination, and death: an international view. *Critical Care*, 24(1), 1-2.
- [80.] Hollis, J. (2020). *Living between worlds: Finding personal resilience in changing times*. Sounds True.
- [81.] Homberg, F., Vogel, R., & Weiherl, J. (2019). Public service motivation and continuous organizational change: Taking charge behaviour at police services. *Public administration*, 97(1), 28-47.
- [82.] Huang, Y. M. (2020). The relationship between networking behavior and promotability: The moderating effect of political skill. *Journal of Management & Organization*, 26(2), 185-200.
- [83.] Humayon, A. A., Raza, S., Amir, H., Hussain, M. S., & Ansari, N. (2018). Assessment of work stress among police in Pakistan. *Journal of applied environmental and biological sciences*, 8(2), 68-73.
- [84.] Iliyasu, R., & Etikan, I. (2021). Comparison of quota sampling and stratified random sampling. *Biom. Biostat. Int. J. Rev*, 10, 24-27.
- [85.] Ismail, H. N., Iqbal, A., & Nasr, L. (2019). Employee engagement and job performance in Lebanon: the mediating role of creativity. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 68(3), 506-523.
- [86.] Jaharuddin, N. S., & Zainol, L. N. (2019). The impact of work-life balance on job engagement and turnover intention. *The South East Asian Journal of Management*, 13(1), 7.
- [87.] Jaiswal, S. (2019). Trial and Error: Finding Your Calling Through Fearless Exploration. <http://hdl.handle.net/10166/5636>
- [88.] Javdani, S. (2019). Policing education: An empirical review of the challenges and impact of the work of school police officers. *American journal of community psychology*, 63(3-4), 253-269.
- [89.] Jensen, U. T., Kjeldsen, A. M., & Vestergaard, C. F. (2020). How is public service motivation affected by regulatory policy changes?. *International Public Management Journal*, 23(4), 465-495.
- [90.] Jeung, D. Y., Kim, C., & Chang, S. J. (2018). Emotional labor and burnout: A review of the literature. *Yonsei medical journal*, 59(2), 187-193.
- [91.] Jindo, T., Kai, Y., Kitano, N., Tsunoda, K., Nagamatsu, T., & Arao, T. (2020). Relationship of workplace exercise with work engagement and psychological distress in employees: A cross-sectional study from the MYLS study. *Preventive medicine reports*, 17, 101030.
- [92.] Jung, H. S., & Yoon, H. H. (2012). The effects of emotional intelligence on counterproductive work behaviors and organizational citizen behaviors among food and beverage employees in a deluxe hotel. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 31(2), 369-378.
- [93.] Karintseva, O. I., Melnyk, L. H., Kubatko, O. V., Dehtyarova, I. B., & Derykolenko, A. O. (2019). Disruptive technologies for the transition of digital economies towards sustainability. <https://essuir.sumdu.edu.ua/handle/123456789/85476>
- [94.] Kašpárková, L., Vaculík, M., Procházka, J., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2018). Why resilient workers perform better: The roles of job satisfaction and work engagement. *Journal of Workplace Behavioral Health*, 33(1), 43-62.
- [95.] Keith, T. Z. (2019). *Multiple regression and beyond: An introduction to multiple regression and structural equation modeling*. Routledge.
- [96.] Kim, J. K., LePine, J. A., & Chun, J. U. (2018). Stuck between a rock and a hard place: Contrasting upward and downward effects of leaders' ingratiation. *Personnel Psychology*, 71(4), 495-518.
- [97.] Kim, T. T., Karatepe, O. M., & Chung, U. Y. (2019). Got political skill? The direct and moderating impact of political skill on stress, tension and outcomes in restaurants. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*.

- [98.] Kim, Y. (2020). Organizational resilience and employee work-role performance after a crisis situation: exploring the effects of organizational resilience on internal crisis communication. *Journal of Public Relations Research*, 32(12), 47-75.
- [99.] Kranefeld, I., Blickle, G., & Meurs, J. (2020). Political skill at work and in careers. In *Oxford research encyclopedia of psychology*.
- [100.] Krause, K. D., & Halkitis, P. N. (2020). Toward a more dynamic understanding of the influence of resilience on health. *Behavioral Medicine*, 46(3-4), 171174.
- [101.] Kulahci, I. G., & Quinn, J. L. (2019). Dynamic relationships between information transmission and social connections. *Trends in ecology & evolution*, 34(6), 545-554.
- [102.] Kuok, A. C. H., & Taormina, R. J. (2017). Work engagement: Evolution of the concept and a new inventory. *Psychological Thought*, 10(2), 262–287.
- [103.] <https://doi.org/10.5964/psyct.v10i2.236>
- [104.] Kwon, H. W. (2020). Performance appraisal politics in the public sector: the effects of political skill and social similarity on performance rating. *Public Personnel Management*, 49(2), 239-261.
- [105.] le May, A., & Elbourne, H. F. (2019). Staying healthy in older age. In *Nursing Older People* (pp. 39-51). Routledge.
- [106.] Ledesma, J. (2014). Conceptual frameworks and research models on resilience in leadership. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/2158244014545464>
- [107.] Lee, J. Y., Choi, J. S., & Kwon, J. S. (2019). Neurophysiological mechanisms of resilience as a protective factor in patients with internet gaming disorder: A resting-state EEG coherence study. *Journal of clinical medicine*, 8(1), 49.
- [108.] Lee, J. Y., Yahiaoui, D., Lee, K. P., & Cooke, F. L. (2022). Global talent management and multinational subsidiaries' resilience in the Covid_19 crisis: Moderating roles of regional headquarters' support and headquarters–subsidiary friction. *Human Resource Management*, 61(3), 355-372.
- [109.] Lee, K. J., Yun, Y. J., & Kim, E. Y. (2019). Political skills and career success of R&D personnel: a comparative mediation analysis between perceived supervisor support and perceived organisational support. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 31(11), 1270-1282.
- [110.] Levitats, Z., & Vigoda_Gadot, E. (2017). Yours emotionally: How emotional intelligence infuses public service motivation and affects the job outcomes of public personnel. *Public Administration*, 95(3), 759-775.
- [111.] Lewis, J. M., Ricard, L. M., & Klijn, E. H. (2018). How innovation drivers, networking and leadership shape public sector innovation capacity. *Revue Internationale des Sciences Administratives*, 84(2), 301-320.
- [112.] Luthans, F. (2002). Positive organizational behavior: Developing and managing psychological strengths. *Academy of Management Executive*, 16, 57–72.
- [113.] Ma, C., Wu, C. H., Jiang, X., & Wei, W. (2019). Why and when leader humility promotes constructive voice: a crossover of energy perspective. *Personnel Review*.
- [114.] Ma, C., Zhou, J., & Yang, D. (2020). Causation analysis of hazardous material road transportation accidents based on the ordered logit regression model. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(4), 1259.
- [115.] Magnusen, M. J., McAllister, C. P., Kim, J. W., Perrewé, P. L., & Ferris, G. R. (2017). The reputation playbook: Exploring how reputation can be leveraged to improve recruiting effectiveness in NCAA men's basketball. *Journal of Applied Sport Management*, 9, 11–24
- [116.] Magnusen, M. J., Mondello, M., Kim, Y. K., & Ferris, G. R. (2011). Roles of recruiter political skill, influence strategy, and organization reputation in recruitment effectiveness in college sports. *Thunderbird International business Review*, 53, 687–700
- [117.] Maher, L. P., Ejaz, A., Nguyen, C. L., & Ferris, G. R. (2021). Forty years of political skill and will in organizations: a review, meta-theoretical framework and directions for future research. *Career Development International*.

- [118.] Majeed, A., Molokhia, M., Pankhania, B., & Asanati, K. (2020). Protecting the health of doctors during the COVID-19 pandemic. *British Journal of General Practice*, 70(695), 268-269.
- [119.] Malik, P., & Garg, P. (2018). Psychometric Testing of the Resilience at Work Scale Using Indian Sample. *Vikalpa*, 43(2), 77–91. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0256090918773922>
- [120.] Malik, P., & Garg, P. (2020). Learning organization and work engagement: The mediating role of employee resilience. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 31(8), 1071-1094.
- [121.] Marenin, O. (2018). Policing change, changing police: Some thematic questions. In *Policing Change, Changing Police* (pp. 3-22). Routledge.
- [122.] Marois, A., Cloutier, M. S., Saunier, N., Godillon, S., Lafond, D., & Vachon, F. (2019). Safety, stress and work zone complexity: A field study on police officers performing on-foot traffic control. *Transportation research interdisciplinary perspectives*, 1, 100018.
- [123.] McAllister, C. P., Ellen III, B. P., Perrewé, P. L., Ferris, G. R., & Hirsch, D. J. (2015). Checkmate: Using political skill to recognize and capitalize on opportunities in the ‘game’ of organizational life. *Business Horizons*, 58(1), 25-34.
- [124.] McEwen, K., & Boyd, C. M. (2018). A measure of team resilience: Developing the resilience at work team scale. *Journal of occupational and environmental medicine*, 60(3), 258-272.
- [125.] Miao, Q., Eva, N., Newman, A., & Schwarz, G. (2019). Public service motivation and performance: The role of organizational identification. *Public Money & Management*, 39(2), 77-85.
- [126.] Miao, Q., Newman, A., Schwarz, G., & Cooper, B. (2018). How leadership and public service motivation enhance innovative behavior. *Public Administration Review*, 78(1), 71-81.
- [127.] Mintzberg, H. 1983. Power in and around organizations. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- [128.] Mueller, R. O., & Hancock, G. R. (2018). Structural equation modeling. In *The reviewer’s guide to quantitative methods in the social sciences* (pp. 445-456). Routledge.
- [129.] Murad, M., Jiatong, W., Shahzad, F., & Syed, N. (2021). The Influence of Despotic Leadership on Counterproductive Work Behavior Among Police Personnel: Role of Emotional Exhaustion and Organizational Cynicism. *Journal of Police and Criminal Psychology*, 36(3), 603-615.
- [130.] Mussagulova, A. (2020). Predictors of work engagement: Drawing on job demands–resources theory and public service motivation. *Australian Journal of Public Administration*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8500.12449>
- [131.] Nevels, T. L., Burch, J. B., Wirth, M. D., Ginsberg, J. P., McLain, A. C., Andrew, M. E., ... & Violanti, J. M. (2021). Shift Work Adaptation Among Police Officers: The BCOPS Study. *Chronobiology international*, 38(6), 907-923.
- [132.] Niemiec, C. P. (2014). Eudaimonic Well-Being. *Encyclopedia of Quality of Life and Well-Being Research*, 2004–2005. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94007-0753-5_929
- [133.] Onyishi, C. N., Ede, M. O., Ossai, O. V., & Ugwuanyi, C. S. (2021). Rational emotive occupational health coaching in the management of police subjective well-being and work ability: a case of repeated measures. *Journal of Police and Criminal Psychology*, 36(1), 96-111.
- [134.] Osborne, S., & Hammoud, M. S. (2017). Effective employee engagement in the workplace. *International Journal of Applied Management and Technology*, 16(1), 4.
- [135.] Papazoglou, K., Koskelainen, M., & Stuewe, N. (2018). Exploring the role of compassion satisfaction and compassion fatigue in predicting burnout among police officers. *Open Journal of Psychiatry & Allied Sciences*, 9(2).
- [136.] Papazoglou, K., Marans, S., Keese, T., & Chopko, B. (2020). Police compassion fatigue. *FBI Law Enforce. Bull*, 1-9.
- [137.] Perry, J. L. (1996). Measuring public service motivation: An assessment of construct reliability and validity. *Journal of Administration Research & Theory*, 6(1), 5–22.
- [138.] Pfeffer, J. (1981). Power in organizations. Boston: Pitman.
- [139.] PhilAtlas. (2022). *Davao Region (Region XI)*. PhilAtlas.com. <https://www.philatlas.com/mindanao/r11.html>

- [140.] Philip, J. (2021). A multi-study approach to examine the interplay of proactive personality and political skill in job crafting. *Journal of Management and Organization*. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jmo.2021.1>
- [141.] Piatak, J. S., Douglas, J. W., & Raudla, R. (2020). The role perceptions of government professionals: The effects of gender, educational field, and prior job sector. *Public Management Review*, 22(10), 1515-1534.
- [142.] Piotrowski, A., Rawat, S., & Boe, O. (2021). Effects of organizational support and organizational justice on police officers' work engagement. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12.
- [143.] Platania, S., Castellano, S., Petralia, M. C., Digrandi, F., Coco, M., Pizzo, M., & Di Nuovo, S. F. (2020). The moderating effect of the dispositional resilience on the relationship between Post-traumatic Stress Disorder and the professional quality of life of the military returning from the peacekeeping operations. *Mediterranean Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 8(3).
- [144.] Prysmakova, P., & Vandenabeele, W. (2020). Enjoying police duties: Public service motivation and job satisfaction. *Journal of police and criminal psychology*, 35(3), 304-317.
- [145.] Puig-Ribera, A., Martínez-Lemos, I., Giné-Garriga, M., González-Suárez, Á. M., Bort-Roig, J., Fortuño, J., ... & Gilson, N. D. (2015). Self-reported sitting time and physical activity: interactive associations with mental well-being and productivity in office employees. *BMC public health*, 15(1), 1-10.
- [146.] Queirós, C., Passos, F., Bártolo, A., Marques, A. J., Da Silva, C. F., & Pereira, A. (2020). Burnout and stress measurement in police officers: Literature review and a study with the operational police stress questionnaire. *Frontiers in psychology*, 11, 587.
- [147.] Quratulain, S., Khan, A. K., & Sabharwal, M. (2019). Procedural fairness, public service motives, and employee work outcomes: Evidence from Pakistani public service organizations. *Review of Public Personnel Administration*, 39(2), 276-299.
- [148.] Rajagukguk, D. H., & Desiana, P. M. (2021). The effect of job resources and public service motivation on affective commitment: The mediating role of work engagement. In *Contemporary Research on Business and Management* (pp. 105-108). CRC Press.
- [149.] Rantatalo, O., & Karp, S. (2018). Stories of policing: The role of storytelling in police students' sensemaking of early work-based experiences. *Vocations and Learning*, 11(1), 161-177.
- [150.] Russell, Z. A., Steffensen, D. S., Ellen III, B. P., Zhang, L., Bishoff, J. D., & Ferris, G. R. (2018). High performance work practice implementation and employee impressions of line manager leadership. *Human Resource Management Review*, 28(3), 258-270.
- [151.] Sabagh, Z., Hall, N. C., & Saroyan, A. (2018). Antecedents, correlates and consequences of faculty burnout. *Educational Research*, 60(2), 131-156.
- [152.] Santa Maria, A., Wolter, C., Gusy, B., Kleiber, D., & Renneberg, B. (2019). The impact of health-oriented leadership on police officers' physical health, burnout, depression and well-being. *Policing: A Journal of Policy and Practice*, 13(2), 186-200.
- [153.] Saunders, J., Kotzias, V., & Ramchand, R. (2019). Contemporary police stress: The impact of the evolving socio-political context. *Actual Probs. Econ. & L.*, 1430.
- [154.] Schermerhorn Jr, J. R., Bachrach, D. G., & Wright, B. (2020). *Management*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [155.] Schütte, N., Blickle, G., Frieder, R. E., Wihler, A., Schnitzler, F., Heupel, J., & Zettler, I. (2018). The role of interpersonal influence in counterbalancing psychopathic personality trait facets at work. *Journal of Management*, 44(4), 1338-1368.
- [156.] Schwarz, G., Eva, N., & Newman, A. (2020). Can public leadership increase public service motivation and job performance?. *Public Administration Review*, 80(4), 543-554.
- [157.] Seitz, S. R., & Misra, K. (2020). Knowledge sharing in social networks: considering the role of political skill and trust. *International Journal of Organization Theory & Behavior*.
- [158.] Shah, H. A., Yasir, M., Majid, A., & Javed, A. (2019). Impact of networking capability on organizational survival of SMEs: Mediating role of strategic renewal. *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences (PJCSS)*, 13(3), 559-580.

- [159.] Sharma, S., & Sharma, S. K. (2020). Probing the links between team resilience, competitive advantage, and organizational effectiveness: Evidence from information technology industry. *Business Perspectives and Research*, 8(2), 289-307.
- [160.] SI Shbail, M., Salleh, Z., & Mohd Nor, N. N. (2018). Antecedents of burnout and its relationship to internal audit quality. *Business and Economic Horizons (BEH)*, 14(1232-2019-871), 789-817.
- [161.] Song, L., Wang, Y., & Zhao, Y. (2021). How employee authenticity shapes work attitudes and behaviors: The mediating role of psychological capital and the moderating role of leader authenticity. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 36(6), 1125-1136.
- [162.] Sosik, J. J., Chun, J. U., Ete, Z., Arenas, F. J., & Scherer, J. A. (2019). Selfcontrol puts character into action: Examining how leader character strengths and ethical leadership relate to leader outcomes. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 160(3), 765-781.
- [163.] Southwick, S. M., & Charney, D. S. (2012). The science of resilience: Implications for the prevention and treatment of depression. *Biol. Psychiatry*, 71(1068).
- [164.] Spence, A. M. (1974). *Market signaling: Information structure of job markets and related phenomena*. Harvard University Press
- [165.] Srivastava, V. K. (2020). Investigating Whether Ecological Models of Community-oriented Variables Improve Prediction of Childhood Resilience Over a Set of Personal Characteristic Variables Such as Impulse Control, Emotional Regulation, Relational Motivation, and Self-reliance.
- [166.] Stancel, K., Russo, C., Koskelainen, M., Papazoglou, K., & Tuttle, B. M. (2019). Police moral injury, compassion fatigue, and compassion satisfaction: A brief report. *Salus Journal*, 7(1), 42-57.
- [167.] Subhashini, R. (2018). Spiritual Interventions for Managing Stress in Police. *SVP National Police Academy*, 114.
- [168.] Sun, L., & Bunchapattanasakda, C. (2019). Employee Engagement: A Literature Review. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 9(1), 63. <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijhrs.v9i1.14167>
- [169.] Susanti, E., & Alwansyah, A. A. (2021). The relationship between counterproductive work behavior and emotional intelligence among pest control employees. *Jurnal Manajemen dan Pemasaran Jasa*, 14(1), 95108.
- [170.] Sutton, A. (2020). Living the good life: A meta-analysis of authenticity, well-being and engagement. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 153, 109645.
- [171.] Taormina, R. J. (2015). Adult personal resilience: A new theory, new measure, and practical implications. *Psychological Thought*, 8(1).
- [172.] Tarka, P. (2018). An overview of structural equation modeling: its beginnings, historical development, usefulness and controversies in the social sciences. *Quality & quantity*, 52(1), 313-354.
- [173.] The Lancet. (2020). The plight of essential workers during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Lancet (London, England)*, 395(10237), 1587.
- [174.] Todak, N. (2017). The decision to become a police officer in a legitimacy crisis. *Women & criminal justice*, 27(4), 250-270.
- [175.] Toth, I., Heinänen, S., & Nisula, A. M. (2020). Personal resources and knowledge workers' job engagement. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*.
- [176.] Treadway, D. C., Adams, G., Hanes, T. J., Perrewe, P. L., Magnusen, M. J., & Ferris, G. R. (2014). The roles of recruiter political skill and performance resource leveraging in NCAA football recruitment effectiveness. *Journal of Management*, 40, 1607–1626
- [177.] Ukhova, N. (2020). Leaders' Resilience in the International Context. *Junior Management Science*, 5(4), 512-531.
- [178.] Uppal, N. (2021). How Machiavellianism engenders impression management motives: The role of social astuteness and networking ability. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 168, 110314.
- [179.] Van Ackeren, M., & Archer, A. (2018). Self-sacrifice and moral philosophy. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies*, 26(3), 301-307.
- [180.] Van den Bosch, R., Taris, T. W., Schaufeli, W. B., Peeters, M. C., & Reijseger, G. (2019). Authenticity at work: a matter of fit?. *The Journal of psychology*, 153(2), 247-266.

- [181.] Van Loon, N., Kjeldsen, A. M., Andersen, L. B., Vandenabeele, W., & Leisink, P. (2018). Only when the societal impact potential is high? A panel study of the relationship between public service motivation and perceived performance. *Review of public personnel administration*, 38(2), 139-166.
- [182.] Van Thielen, T., Bauwens, R., Audenaert, M., Van Waeyenberg, T., & Decramer, (2018). How to foster the well-being of police officers: The role of the employee performance management system. *Evaluation and program planning*, 70, 90-98.
- [183.] Van Witteloostuijn, A., Esteve, M., & Boyne, G. (2017). Public sector motivation ad fonts: Personality traits as antecedents of the motivation to serve the public interest. *Journal of public administration research and theory*, 27(1), 20-35.
- [184.] Veilleux, J., Pollert, G., Skinner, K. D., Baker, D. E., Chamberlain, K. D., & Hill, M. A. (2019). Individual beliefs about emotion and perceptions of belief stability are associated with emotion dysregulation, interpersonal emotional attributes and psychological flexibility.
- [185.] Verma, T. S., & Pearl, J. (2022). Equivalence and synthesis of causal models. In *Probabilistic and Causal Inference: The Works of Judea Pearl* (pp. 221-236).
- [186.] Walpita, Y. N., & Arambepola, C. (2020). High resilience leads to better work performance in nurses: Evidence from South Asia. *Journal of nursing management*, 28(2), 342-350.
- [187.] Wang, M. Z., & Hall, J. A. (2019). Political skill and outcomes in social life. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 149, 192-199.
- [188.] Wang, Y., Luo, W., Zhang, J., & Guo, Y. (2019). More humility, less counterproductive work behaviors? The role of interpersonal justice and trust. *Frontiers of Business Research in China*, 13(1), 1-18.
- [189.] Waycott, J., Vetere, F., & Ozanne, E. (2019). Building social connections: a framework for enriching older adults' social connectedness through information and communication technologies. In *Ageing and digital technology* (pp. 65-82). Springer, Singapore.
- [190.] Weaver, G. R., Reynolds, S. J., and Brown, M. E. (2014). Moral intuition: connecting current knowledge to future organizational research and practice. *J. Manage.* 40, 100–129. doi: 10.1177/0149206313511272
- [191.] Wee, M., Ahmad, N. H., Sadik, M. Z., Abd Razak, N., & Marmaya, N. H. (2019). Coaching millennial entrepreneurs in tourism industry: a glimpse of political skill. *Journal of International Business, Economics and Entrepreneurship*, 4(2), 1-7.
- [192.] Wihler, A., Frieder, R. E., & Blicke, G. (2018, July). The effects of networking ability and apparent sincerity on voice recognition and capitalization. In *Academy of Management Proceedings* (Vol. 2018, No. 1, p. 11062). Briarcliff Manor, NY 10510: Academy of Management.
- [193.] Willis, J. J., & Mastrofski, S. D. (2018). Improving policing by integrating craft and science: what can patrol officers teach us about good police work?. *Policing and society*, 28(1), 27-44.
- [194.] Wolter, C., Santa Maria, A., Georg, S., Lesener, T., Gusy, B., Kleiber, D., & Renneberg, B. (2021). Relationships between effort-reward imbalance and work engagement in police officers: taking a salutogenic perspective. *Journal of Public Health*, 29, 177-186.
- [195.] Wolter, C., Santa Maria, A., Wörfel, F., Gusy, B., Lesener, T., Kleiber, D., & Renneberg, B. (2019). Job demands, job resources, and well-being in police officers—a resource-oriented approach. *Journal of Police and Criminal Psychology*, 34(1), 45-54.
- [196.] Xu, N., Chiu, C. Y., & Treadway, D. C. (2019). Tensions between diversity and shared leadership: The role of team political skill. *Small Group Research*, 50(4), 507-538.
- [197.] Xu, S., Yang, T., Guo, R., & Zhang, W. (2019). The antecedents and consequences of employees' followership behavior in social network organizational context: a longitudinal study. *EURASIP Journal on Wireless Communications and Networking*, 2019(1), 1-14.
- [198.] Yeung, M. S. (2021). Finding a Calling: Carter's Transcontinental Journey to Chinese Studies. In *An American Pioneer of Chinese Studies in CrossCultural Perspective* (pp. 32-67). Brill.
- [199.] Yin, N. (2018). The influencing outcomes of job engagement: an interpretation from the social exchange theory. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*.

- [200.] Yu, J., Li, H., & Xiao, H. (2020). Are authentic tourists happier? Examining structural relationships amongst perceived cultural distance, existential authenticity, and wellbeing. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 22(1), 144-154.
- [201.] Zhang, S. E., Wang, X., Shi, Y., Liu, B., Huang, X., Wang, H., ... & Sun, T. (2021). What motivates individual public service motivation and cooperation at the initial stage of the COVID_19 outbreak: A cross_sectional survey. *The International journal of health planning and management*.
- [202.] Zhou, F., & Wu, Y. J. (2018). How humble leadership fosters employee innovation behavior: A two-way perspective on the leader-employee interaction. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*.

APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

APPOINTMENT OF ADVISER

Professional Schools

Ground Floor, PS Building Matina, Davao City

Telefax: (082) 305-0645 Local 189

April 6, 2022

EUGENIO S. GUHAO, JR., DM

Dean

Professional Schools

Dear Dean Guhao:

Since Dr. Victoria O. Ligan has separated from the University for health reasons, may I ask for her replacement as my dissertation adviser. The title of my research is "POLITICAL SKILLS, RESILIENCE AT WORK, AND PUBLIC SERVICE MOTIVATION: A STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODEL ON JOB ENGAGEMENT OF POLICE PERSONNEL IN REGION XI."

May I respectfully request Dr. Alberto N. Bandiola to be my new adviser?

Thank you for your kind approval.

April 16, 2022
 DR. EUGENIO N. GUHAO -
 n
 Professional Schools
 Dear,
 recommending approval. Thank you.
 [Signature]

JUAN C. CHAVEZ JR.
DPA, Student

APPENDIX B
SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Sir/Madam:

I am working on my dissertation titled "A STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODEL ON JOB ENGAGEMENT OF POLICE PERSONNEL IN REGION XI". In this connection, I respectfully request your kind help in answering my questionnaire. Your truthful answers to the questions will genuinely make this study meaningful. I assure you of the utmost confidentiality of your answers, which will be for this research only.

Please do not leave any items blank. Thank you.

Respectfully yours,

PMAJ JUAN C CHAVEZ JR
Researcher

Rank/Full Name: (Optional) _____

Unit Address/Assignment: _____

Questionnaire on
**A STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODEL ON JOB ENGAGEMENT OF
POLICE PERSONNEL IN REGION XI**

Please express how you feel about each statement by putting a check mark in the box describing your level of agreement or disagreement. For example, you may tick (✓) **5** for **Strongly Agree**, **4** for **Agree**, **3** for **Neutral**, **2** for **Disagree**, and **1** for **Strongly Disagree**.

Please refer to the Rating Scale below with its description and interpretation.

Rating	Description	Interpretation
5	Strongly Agree (SA)	The idea/act described in the statement always happens.
4	Agree (A)	The idea/act described in the statement often happens.
3	Neutral (N)	The idea/act described in the statement happens sometimes.
2	Disagree (D)	The idea/act described in the statement happens rarely.
1	Strongly Disagree (SD)	The idea/act described in the statement never happens.

Part I. POLITICAL SKILL

NETWORKING ABILITY

- 1 I spend a lot of time and effort at work networking with others.
- 2 I am good at building relationships with influential people at work.
- 3 I have developed an extensive network of colleagues and associates at work support when I need to get things done. n I can call on for
- 4 At work, I know many influential people and am well-connected.
- 5 I spend a lot of time at work developing connections with others.
- 6 I am good at using my connections and network to make things happen at work.

INTERPERSONAL INFLUENCE

- 1 I can make most people feel comfortable and at ease around me.
- 2 I can communicate efficiently and effectively with others.
- 3 It is easy for me to develop a good rapport with most people.
- 4 I am good at getting people to like me.

SOCIAL ASTUTENESS

- 1 I understand people very well.
- 2 I am particularly good at sensing the motivations and hidden agendas of others.
- 3 I have a good intuition or savvy about how to present myself to others.
- 4 I always instinctively know the right things to say or do to influence others.
- 5 I pay close attention to people's facial expressions.

APPARENT SINCERITY

- 1 When communicating with others, I try to be genuine in what I say and do.
- 2 People must believe I am sincere in what I say and do.
- 3 I try to show a genuine interest in other people.
- 4 I pay close attention to people's facial expressions.

Part II. RESILIENCE AT WORK

LIVING AUTHENTICALLY

- 1 I have essential core values that I hold fast in my work life.
- 2 I know my strengths and use them regularly in my work.
- 3 I can change my mood at work when I need to.

FINDING YOUR CALLING

- 1 My work helps to fulfill my sense of purpose in life.
- 2 My workplace is somewhere where I feel that I belong.
- 3 Generally, I appreciate what I have in my work environment.

MAINTAINING PERSPECTIVE

- 1 I am not intimidated by anything in my work.
- 2 I am not affected by negative people at work.

MANAGING STRESS

- 1 I make sure I take breaks to maintain my strength and energy when I am working hard.
- 2 I have developed reliable ways to relax under pressure at work.
- 3 I have developed reliable ways to deal with the stress of challenging events at work.
- 4 I am careful to ensure my work does not dominate my personal life.

BUILDING SOCIAL CONNECTIONS

- 1 I often ask for feedback so that I can improve my work performance.
- 2 I have friends at work I can rely on to support me when I need them.
- 3 I have a robust and reliable network of supportive colleagues at work.

STAYING HEALTHY

- 1 I have a good level of physical fitness.
- 2 I am careful about eating healthy.

Part III. PUBLIC SERVICE MOTIVATION

SELF-SACRIFICE

- 1 I am prepared to make enormous sacrifices for the good of society.
- 2 I believe in putting duty before self.
- 3 Serving other citizens would give me a good feeling even if no one paid me for it.

ATTRACTION TO POLICYMAKING

- 1 Sharing my views on public policies with others is attractive to me.
- 2 Seeing people benefit from the public program I have been deeply involved in brings me great satisfaction.
- 3 I am interested in making public programs that benefit my country or the community I belong.
- 4 I consider public service my civic duty.
- 5 Meaningful public service is significant to me.

COMPASSION

- 1 Daily events often remind me how dependent we are on one another.
- 2 I feel sympathetic for the plight of the underprivileged.
- 3 Making a difference in society means more to me than personal achievements.

Part IV. WORK ENGAGEMENT

COGNITIVE WORK ENGAGEMENT

- 1 My mind is often full of ideas about my work.
- 2 Wherever I am, things happen that often remind me of my work.
- 3 My mind is fully engaged with my work.
- 4 I rarely think about the time when I am working.
- 5 My thoughts are entirely focused when thinking about my work.
- 6 I give a lot of mental attention to my work.

EMOTIONAL WORK ENGAGEMENT

- 1 I feel delighted about what I am doing whenever I am working.
- 2 I am very eager to do my work.
- 3 I feel delighted when I am carrying out my responsibilities at work.
- 4 I feel terrific about the work that I do.
- 5 I feel a strong enthusiasm for my work.
- 6 I feel a sense of gratification with my work performance.

PHYSICAL WORK ENGAGEMENT

- 1 No matter how much I work, I have a high energy level.
- 2 I have a great deal of stamina for my work.
- 3 I always have a lot of energy for my work.
- 4 I am often physically driven by my work.
- 5 My work frequently energizes me.
- 6 I find my work to be physically stimulating.

-END-

Rev. # 0/ Effectivity: July 14, 2020

APPENDIX C

LETTERS TO THE VALIDATORS

PROFESSIONAL SCHOOLS

Main Branch _____

LETTER TO THE VALIDATOR

February 3, 2022

FATMA M. IDRIS, DRD
Ret. Regional Director, BFAR XI
Davao City

Dear Dr. Idris:

The undersigned would like to request you to validate the survey tool for his dissertation titled "A STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODEL ON JOB ENGAGEMENT OF POLICE PERSONNEL IN REGION XI," as a requirement for the Doctor in Public Administration (DPA). Undoubtedly, your expertise would make the survey tool rich and substantive in content.

Attached to this request is the printout of the actual survey instrument and the study's research objectives. Your comments and suggestions will significantly help in refining the survey tool.

Thank you for your favorable response to this request.

Rev. # 0/ Effectivity: July 14, 2020

Sincerely,

Rev. # 0/ Effectivity: July 14, 2020

✓ ✓

JUAN C. CHAVEZ, JR.
Researcher

Noted by:

ALBERTO N. BANDIOLA, DPA
Research Adviser

February 3, 2022

JOEL B. TAN, DBA
Research Coordinator
UMPS

Dear Dr. Tan:

The undersigned would like to request you to validate the survey tool for his dissertation titled "A STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODEL ON JOB ENGAGEMENT OF POLICE PERSONNEL IN REGION XI," as a requirement for the Doctor in Public Administration (DPA). Undoubtedly, your expertise would make the survey tool rich and substantive in content.

Attached to this request is the printout of the actual survey instrument and the study's research objectives. Your comments and suggestions will significantly help in refining the survey tool.

Thank you for your favorable response to this request.

Sincerely,

Rev. # 0/ Effectivity: July 14, 2020

JUAN C. CHAVEZ, JR.
Researcher

Noted by:

ALBERTO N. BANDIOLA, DPA
Research Adviser

PROFESSIONAL SCHOOLS
[X] Main [] Branch _____
LETTER TO THE VALIDATOR

February 3, 2022

ALGER P. DURA, DPA
DPA Program Technical Assist.
UM Professional Schools

Dear Dr. Dura:

The undersigned would like to request you to validate the survey tool for his dissertation titled "A STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODEL ON JOB ENGAGEMENT OF POLICE PERSONNEL IN REGION XI," as a requirement for the Doctor in Public Administration (DPA). Undoubtedly, your expertise would make the survey tool rich and substantive in content.

Attached to this request is the printout of the actual survey instrument and the study's research objectives. Your comments and suggestions will significantly help in refining the survey tool.

Thank you for your favorable response to this request.

Sincerely,

JUAN C. CHAVEZ, JR.
Researcher

Rev. # 0/ Effectivity: July 14, 2020

Noted by:

ALBERTO N. BANDIOLA, DPA
Research Adviser

PROFESSIONAL SCHOOLS

Main Branch _____

LETTER TO THE VALIDATOR

February 3, 2022

JED P. ACERO, DPA
Department of Education
Davao City

Dear Dr. Acero:

The undersigned would like to request you to validate the survey tool for his dissertation titled "A STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODEL ON JOB ENGAGEMENT OF POLICE PERSONNEL IN REGION XI," as a requirement for the Doctor in Public Administration (DPA). Undoubtedly, your expertise would make the survey tool rich and substantive in content.

Attached to this request is the printout of the actual survey instrument and the study's research objectives. Your comments and suggestions will significantly help in refining the survey tool.

Thank you for your favorable response to this request.

Sincerely,

JUAN C. CHAVEZ, JR.
Researcher

Noted by:

ALBERTO N. BANDIOLA, DPA
Research Adviser

February 3, 2022

MA. LUISA B. FAUNILLAN, DPA
University of Southeastern Philippines
Obrero, Davao City

Dear Dr. Faunillan:

The undersigned would like to request you to validate the survey tool for his dissertation titled "A STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODEL ON JOB ENGAGEMENT OF POLICE PERSONNEL IN REGION XI," as a requirement for the Doctor in Public Administration (DPA). Undoubtedly, your expertise would make the survey tool rich and substantive in content.

Attached to this request is the printout of the actual survey instrument and the study's research objectives. Your comments and suggestions will significantly help in refining the survey tool.

Thank you for your favorable response to this request.

Sincerely,

JUAN C. CHAVEZ, JR.
Researcher

Noted by:

ALBERTO N. BANDIOLA, DPA
Research Adviser

APPENDIX D

VALIDATION SHEETS

 The University of Mindanao	<h2 style="margin: 0;">PROFESSIONAL SCHOOLS</h2> [] Main [] Branch _____
VALIDATION SHEET FOR RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE	
Name of Evaluator : Degree : Position : Number of Years of Teaching : To the Evaluator : Points of Equivalent :	ALGER P. DURA Doctor in Public Administration DPA Program Tech. Assistant Please check the appropriate box for your ratings 5 - Excellent 2 - Fair 4 - Very Good 1 - Poor 3 - Good
ITEMS	5 4 3 2 1
1. Clarity of Directions and Items The vocabulary level, language, structure and conceptual level of questions suit the level of participants. The directions and the items are written in a clear and simple language.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
2. Presentation and Organization of Items The items are presented and organized in logical manner.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
3. Suitability of Items The item is appropriate and represents the substance of the research. The questions are designed to determine the conditions, knowledge, perception and attitudes that are supposed to be measured.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
4. Adequateness of Items per Category or Indicator The items represent the coverage of research adequately. The questions per area category are adequate representations of all the questions needed for research.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
5. Attainment of Purpose The instrument fulfills the objectives for which it was constructed.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
6. Objectivity Each item questions only one specific answer or measures only one behavior and no aspect of the questionnaire is a suggestion of the researcher.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
7. Scale and Evaluation Rating Scale The scale adapted is appropriate for the items.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Title of Approved Research: <u>A Structural Equation Model on Job Engagement of Police Personnel in Region XI</u>	
Name of Researcher: <u>JUAN C. CHAVEZ, JR.</u>	
Research Adviser: <u>ALBERTO N. BANDIOLA, DPA</u>	
Date of Evaluation of the Questionnaire: <u>02-11-22</u>	
Remarks of the Evaluator: _____ _____	
 ALGER P. DURA, DPA Signature Above Printed Name	

F-13550-011/ Rev. # 3/ Effectivity: January 25, 2018

 The University of Mindanao	<h2 style="margin: 0;">PROFESSIONAL SCHOOLS</h2> [✓] Main [] Branch _____																																																
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<p> Name of Evaluator : DR. MA. LUISA B. FAUNILLAN Degree : DPA Position : VPAA, USEP Number of Years of Teaching : _____ To the Evaluator : _____ Please check the appropriate box for your ratings Points of Equivalent : _____ </p> <table style="margin-left: 100px; border: none;"> <tr> <td style="padding-right: 20px;">5- Excellent</td> <td>2- Fair</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4- Very Good</td> <td>1- Poor</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3- Good</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>		5- Excellent	2- Fair	4- Very Good	1- Poor	3- Good																																											
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Name of Evaluator : GLENNE BERJA LAGURA Degree : Doctor in Public Administration Position : Assistant Professor IV Number of Years of Teaching : 11 years To the Evaluator : Please check the appropriate box for your ratings Points of Equivalent : <table style="display: inline-table; vertical-align: middle; margin-left: 20px;"> <tr> <td>5- Excellent</td> <td>2- Fair</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4- Very Good</td> <td>1- Poor</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3- Good</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>		5- Excellent	2- Fair	4- Very Good	1- Poor	3- Good	
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 GLENNE E. LAGURA, DPA Signature Above Printed Name							

F-13550-011/ Rev. # 3/ Effectivity: January 25, 2018

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Name of Evaluator : <u>JED P. ACERO</u> Degree : <u>Doctor of Public Administration</u> Position : <u>Teacher, DepEd</u> Number of Years of Teaching : _____ To the Evaluator : _____ Points of Equivalent : _____	Please check the appropriate box for your ratings 5 - Excellent 2 - Fair 4 - Very Good 1 - Poor 3 - Good				
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Name of Researcher: <u>JUAN CHAVEZ</u>					
Research Adviser: <u>DR. VICTORIA O. LIGAN/DR. ALBERTO N. BANDIOLA</u>					
Date of Evaluation of the Questionnaire: <u>2/11/2022</u>					
Remarks of the Evaluator: <u>for implementation and administration</u>					
<u>(SGD.) JED P. ACERO, D</u> Signature Above Printed N					

F-13550-011/ Rev. # 3/ Effectivity: January 25, 2018

APPENDIX E

SUMMARY OF VALIDATORS' RATINGS AND CRONBACH'S ALPHA/PILOT TESTING RESULT

SUMMARY OF VALIDATORS' RATINGS

	Name of Validator	Items							Total
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
1	Dr. Alberto N. Bandiola	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	34
2	Dr. Alger P. Dura	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	35
3	Dr. Fatma M. Idris	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	35
4	Dr. Glenne B. Lagura	3	4	5	5	5	4	5	31
5	Dr. Jed P. Acero	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	35
6	Dr. Maria Luisa B. Faunillan	5	5	5	3	4	5	5	32
		28	28	30	28	29	29	30	202
		VALIDITY INDEX							4.81

CRONBACH'S ALPHA AND PILOT TESTING RESULT

INTERPRETATION	
Interpreting ALPHA for dichotomous or Likert scale question.	
CRONBACH'S α	INTERNAL CONSISTENCY
0.90 and above	Excellent
0.80 - 0.89	Good
0.70 - 0.79	Acceptable
0.60 - 0.69	Questionable
0.50 - 0.59	Poor
below 0.50	Unacceptable

<https://www.statisticshowto.com/cronbachs-alpha-sps/>

I - POLITICAL SKILLS

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.969	.970	19

III-PUBLIC SERVICE MOTIVATION

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.952	.954	10

II – RESILIENCE AT WORK

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.957	.958	17

IV-WORK ENGAGEMENT

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.977	.978	18

APPENDIX F

LETTER TO CONDUCT THE STUDY

Professional Schools

Ground Floor, PS Building Matina, Davao City
Telefax: (082)305-0645 Local 189

February 3, 2022

PBGEN FILMORE BONDILLES ESCOBAL

Regional Director, Police Regional Office 11
Camp Sgt. Quintin M. Merezido
Buhangin, Davao City

Dear **Gen. Escobal**:

The undersigned is currently working on his dissertation titled, "**A Structural Equation Model on Job Engagement of Police Personnel in Region XI,**" as a requirement for the degree of Doctor in Public Administration (DPA).

In this regard, the researcher would like to request your approval to conduct the study in your area of responsibility. Respondents of this study are the policemen assigned to the Davao City Police Office (DCPO), Davao Del Sur Police Provincial Office (DSPPO), Davao Occidental Police Provincial Office (DOCCPPO), Davao Del Norte Police Provincial Office (DNPPPO), Davao De Oro Police Provincial Office (DDOPPO), and Davao Oriental Police Provincial Office (DOPPO).

Rest assured that the observance of confidentiality of the data will be the utmost priority. Attached herewith are the research objectives and the survey questionnaire for your information.

Thank you for your favorable response to this request.

Respectfully yours,

JUAN C. CHAVEZ JR.
Researcher

ALBERTO N. BANDIOLA, DPA
Research Adviser

Noted by:

EUGENIO S. GUHAO, JR., DM
Dean

APPENDIX G

TURNITIN RESULT

APPENDIX H
GRAMMARIAN'S CERTIFICATION

Appendix I

UMERC’S CERTIFICATION WITH INFORM CONSENT FORM FOR UMERC CERTIFICATE (TO BE ATTACHED LATER)

University of Mindanao

Informed Consent Form (ICF)

UMERC - 006 Rev. 01 / December 1, 2016
--

Control No.: _____

PARTICIPATION AND WITHDRAWAL

Your participation is voluntary. Your refusal to participate will involve no penalty or loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled. You may withdraw your consent at any time and discontinue participation without penalty. You are not waiving any legal claims, rights or remedies because of your participation in this research study.

INVESTIGATOR’S CONTACT INFORMATION

If you have any questions or concerns about the research, please feel free to contact the researcher at 134-Binayug Street, Purok 9, Barangay Communal, Buhangin District, Davao City; through mobile phone number 09186655946 or through email at pijunchavez@gmail.com; or if you need to see him, he can be located at the Regional Training Center 11, Mintal, Davao City.

RIGHTS OF RESEARCH PARTICIPANT

If you have questions, concerns, or complaints about your right as a research participant or the research in general and are unable to contact the research team, or if you want to talk to someone independent of the research team, please contact the University of Mindanao Professional Schools at 305-06-45

RESEARCH PARTICIPANT’S CONSENT

I have read the information provided above. I have been given a chance to ask questions. My questions have been answered to my satisfaction, and I agree to participate in this study. I have been given a copy of this form. I can withdraw my consent at any time and discontinue participation without penalty.

Signature above Printed Name of Participant

April 4, 2022
Date Signed

To be accomplished by the Researcher Obtaining Consent:

I have explained the research to the participant and answered all of his/her questions. I believe that he/she understands the information described in this document and freely consents to participate.

Juan C./Chavez Jr.
Person Obtaining Consent

April 4, 2022
Date Signed

Name of

APPENDIX J

CERTIFICATE OF PUBLICATION

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INNOVATIVE
SCIENCE AND RESEARCH TECHNOLOGY**

IJISRT A DIGITAL LIBRARY

ISSN NO :- 2456-2165

AUTHOR CERTIFICATE

THIS IS TO CERTIFY THAT THE MANUSCRIPT, ENTITLED
Political Skills, Resilience at Work, and Public Service Motivation: A Structural
Equation Model on Job Engagement of Police Personnel in Region XI

AUTHORED BY
Juan C. Chavez Jr

HAS BEEN PUBLISHED IN
Volume 7 | Issue 10 | October - 2022

ARTICLE DIGITAL NO.
IJISRT22OCT080

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To verify the submitted manuscript please visit our official website: www.ijisrt.com
Or Email us: editor@ijisrt.com

WWW.IJISRT.COM

CURRICULUM VITAE**PMAJ JUAN C. CHAVEZ, JR.,**

AB-PHILISOPHY, BS CRIM, MACT-LEA, and JURIS DOCTOR

134-Binayug Street, Purok 9, Camp Quinting M Mercialdo,

Buhangin, Davao City, Davao del Sur, Philippines

Mobile: +639186655946

Email: pijunchavez@gmail.com

EDUCATION

<i>Doctor of Public Administration Student, University Of Mindanao</i>	Year
	2018
<i>SAL Foundation College, Parang, Maguindanao</i>	
Bachelor of Science in Criminology	2014
BS Criminology	2010
<i>University of Mindanao</i>	2002
Master of Arts in College Teaching-Law Enforcement Administration	1998
MACT-LEA	
	1997
<i>University of Mindanao</i>	1993
Bachelor of Legal Luminary	
LLB	
	1989
<i>Notre Dame University</i>	1983
AB-Philosophy	
Bachelor of Arts	
	1982
Malinao Barangay High School	1978
Secondary Education	
Malinao Elementary School	1978
Elementary Education	1972

ELIGIBILITIES

Police Inspector	NAPOLCOM Exam	Oct. 24, 1994
Senior Police Officer	NAPOLCOM Exam	Oct. 28, 2001
Police Officer 111	NAPOLCOM Exam	Nov. 24, 1991

SCHOOLING AWARDS

Leadership Award 1 st Placer	Public Safety Officer Basic Course Public Safety Officer Candidate Course RTC 11	2015
Leadership Award	Public Safety Officer Candidate Course RTC 11	2012
Academic Award 2 nd Placer	Public Safety Officer Candidate Course RTC 11	2012
Top Comprehensive Exam RTC 11	Public Safety Officers Candidate Course	2012

THESIS

- Intellectual Love of Baruch Spinoza - AB-Philosophy Graduate, Notre Dame University Cotabato City for CY 1989
- Administrative Cases of Erring Police Personnel in Region 11 - MACT-LEA Graduate, the University of Mindanao for CY 2004

MANDATORY SCHOOLING RTS 11

Public Safety Officers Basic Course (PSOBC)	2015
Public Safety Officers Candidate Course (PSOCC)	2012
Public Safety Senior Leadership Course(PSSLC)	2006
Public Safety Junior Leadership Course(PSJLC)	2004
Police Basic Course (PBC)	1991

MEMBERSHIPS

- Corps of Professors RTC11
- Summary Hearing Officers RIAS 11
- Philippine National Police Prosecutors
- Police Regional Office 11 Tennis Club

PNP SERVICE RECORDS

• Provincial Superintendent, DDOPIAS	2020-2021
• Provincial Superintendent, DOPIAS	2016-2020
• Provincial Director, COMVAL PIAS	2014-2016
• Chief, IAD & SHO, RIAS XI	2012-2014
• Provincial Director, DO PIAS	2010-2012
• Reviewing Officer and SHO, RIAS XI	2010-2011
• Chief, IAD & SHO	2009-2010
• Summary Hearing Officer (SHO), RIAS XI	2008-2009
• Chief, Inspection and Audit (IAD), RIAS XI	2006-2008
• Prosecutor/Investigator, RIAS XI	2005-2006
• Prosecutor/Investigator, CIAS	1998-2005
• Prosecutor/Investigator, PRO XI	1997-1998
• Officer-In-Charge, Media, Congress and School Program, PCR, PRO XI	1993-1997
• Rifleman 437 Mobile Force Company, Lapinigan, Mabini, Davao del Norte	1993-1991